
Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

Grant agreement: 730423
From March 2017 to June 2020

Prepared by: RINA-C

Date: 31/05/2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730423.

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.:	D6.6
Deliverable Name:	Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations
Responsible Partner:	Rina Consulting S.p.A.
WP no. and title:	WP6 Cross sectorial validation, replicability and Upscaling of solutions
Task no. and title:	T6.3 Overcoming legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging
Version:	v 0.0
Version Date:	31/05/2020

Dissemination level	
X	PU = Public
	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals

	Company
Author/s	RINA-C, with contributions from: BUMAGA CIRCE CRF EKO FATER ICLEI KARTAL MUN MI-PLAST OCU NOVAMONT SAPONIA
Task Leader	RINA-C
WP Leader	EKODENGE
Reviewer	AITIIP, CIRCE, EKO and Task Partners

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730423".

This document has been prepared by CIRC-PACK project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the EC-GA contract no 730423.

Neither Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of CIRC-PACK Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- (a) makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, expressed or implied,
 - (i). with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, or
 - (ii). that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property, or
 - (iii). that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- (b) assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if the Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the CIRC-PACK Project Consortium Agreement has been informed of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

ABBREVIATIONS

AHP	Absorbent Hygienic Product
CIRC-PACK	Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain
D	Deliverable
DC	Demo Case
EoW	End of Waste
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
PS	Polystyrene
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear low density polyethylene
PE	Polyethylene
EU	European Union
MS	Member State
JRC	Joint Research Centre
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

List of participants	
Participant No/Participant legal name	Participant short name
1/ (Coord) CIRCE – Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos	CIRCE
2/ Fundación ATIIP	ATIIP
3/ NOVAMONT S.p.A.	NOVAMONT
4/ MATER-BIOTECH SPA	MATER
5/ Mater-Biopolymer	MBP
6/ BUMAGA BV BV	BUMAGA BV
7/ Tecnopackaging	TECNO
8/ Mi-Plast doo za proizvodnju trgovinu I pruzane usluga – Mi-Plast LCC	MIPLAST
9/ Grupo SADA P.A. S.A.	SADA
10/ SAPONIA D. D. kemijska, prehrambena i farma ceutska industrija d.d.	SAPONIA
11/ FATER Spa	FATER
12/ Centro Ricerche Fiat	CRF
13/ Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación	AENOR
14/ D'APPOLONIA SPA	DAPP
15/ Ekodenge muhendislik mimarlik danismanlik ticaret anonym sirketi	EKO
16/ Ecoembalajes España SA	ECOEMBES
17/ Grad Rijeka	RIJEKA
18/ Kartal Belediye Başkanlığı	KARTAL MUN
19/ CALAF INDUSTRIAL	CALAF
20/ OCU Ediciones	OCU
21/ ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH	ICLEI
22/ PLASTIPOLIS	PLASTIPOLIS

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This Deliverable has the overall aim to identify a set of policy recommendations for EU institutions to promote and facilitate circular economy-based schemes for plastic packaging streams, with a focus on the recycling phase.

In detail, an **overview of the existing policy framework** addressing waste management and plastic packaging in particular is presented, in order to understand and review the existing measures to improve circularity in the entire value chain. It includes legislative updates from December 2018 at **EU level**, such as the Final Circular Economy Package, addressing also specifically the plastics sector.

Updates are presented also at **national level** for Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey (already analysed in previous deliverables of the project). From the analysis it appears that major progress has been reached in Italy, where new End of Waste (EoW) criteria have been adopted and where a plastic tax has entered in force (unless any future modification caused by the COVID-19 crisis) and Croatia, where an improvement of the sorting and collection of municipal waste is pursued. For a selection of additional Countries among those that adopted the first Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive in 1994, the deliverable includes synthetic factsheets, showing the main features and peculiarities of waste management in each country. Such factsheets show main approaches to urban waste management and differences from one country to another, serving as supporting information for the final development of the policy recommendations.

Then, starting from the analyses performed in previous deliverable of the project, from the analysis of the existing policy framework and from an extensive desk analysis, a selection of **barriers to circular economy in plastic packaging value chain** is identified. The barriers are classified into general legislative, supply chain, economic, awareness and engagement, technological and design, traceability and standardization barriers as well as biobased, biodegradable and compostable materials specific barriers. In parallel, a selection of **measures to overcome the identified barriers** is proposed. Differently, from the case of the barriers, they are not categorized into different groups as it is quite common that a single measure addresses multiple barriers, of multiple types.

In this sense, the work performed has clearly highlighted how all the phases of the plastic packaging value chain, from manufacturing, through sorting and collection to recycling are interconnected, and that – at high scale - it may not be advantageous to focus on an extrapolated phase while not considering the others. The enhancement of circular economy in the plastic packaging sector appears to be driven by a number of factors, stimulating improvements at different stages of the value chain, which however become fully effective only if complemented one with another.

A **public stakeholders' consultation** investigating the importance of the identified barriers and of the desirability of the measures has been drafted and shared.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

It results that barriers with an overall importance higher or equal to 90% belong to variegated categories, namely economic (2/4 barriers), technological and design (2/4 barriers), general legislative (2/6 barriers), supply chain (1/3 barriers), awareness and engagement (1/2 barriers). None of the barriers belonging to the traceability and standardization category and addressing biobased, biodegradable and compostable specific issue exceeds 90% of importance. However, it shall be highlighted that all the barriers were highlighted as important or very important by the majority of the respondents.

As for the measures, it appears that the measures ensuring a significant and constant demand for sustainable products, from large companies or public authorities are firmly desired, mostly at EU and national level. In addition, the measures addressing the establishment of a more effective waste management systems, especially on behalf of the consumers are encouraged, mostly at EU level and at national level as far as awareness raising initiatives are concerned.

The results of the consultation for both measures and barriers towards circular economy in the plastic packaging sector are also compared against the outcomes and highlights of the relevant **stakeholders' meeting** performed along the project with the involvement of RINA-C, in which the issues subject of this Deliverable were discussed in order to obtain more solid results.

Subsequently, a **focus on EoW criteria** is presented. It includes a brief introduction, an analysis of existing specific legislation and an insight about stakeholders' opinions about EoW criteria and their potential adoption, with close reference to CIRCPACK value chains. There is large agreement on the high fragmentation of EoW legislation and rules within EU, leading to consensus about the need of establishing – independently of the specific waste flow - a more homogeneous legislative background at EU level in order to allow a growth of circular market segments as well as to increase confidence and stability among investors and stakeholders.

As ultimate result of all the activities described, the following **policy recommendations** facilitating the recycling of biodegradable and fossil-based plastics and enhancing circularity in the plastic packaging value chain are presented:

- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling)** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria** – to be adopted at least at national level;

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

- **reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions** – to be adopted at least at national level, but possibly also at EU level;
- **encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics** – to be adopted at least at EU level – to be adopted at least at EU level.

It is also worth mentioning that in October 2018, the partial results of the activities of T6.3 were used – together with other partners' inputs – to fill on behalf on the CIRCPACK's consortium the **stakeholders' consultation "Future climate and energy policy - a Strategy for long-term EU greenhouse gas emissions reductions"** launched by the European Commission.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	11
2	Policy framework.....	12
2.1	EU level	12
2.1.1	Sustainable Products in a Circular Economy - Towards an EU Product Policy Framework contributing to the Circular Economy	12
2.1.2	Final Circular Economy Package and Circular Economy for Plastics	12
2.1.3	Directive (EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment	13
2.1.4	The European Green Deal.....	14
2.2	National level	15
2.2.1	Updates from D6.3	15
2.2.1.1	Italy	15
2.2.1.2	Spain	15
2.2.1.3	Croatia	16
2.2.1.4	Turkey.....	16
2.2.2	Overview across Member States	17
3	Barriers to circular economy in plastic packaging value chain	20
3.1	Previous findings of D6.4	20
3.2	Update of barriers.....	21
3.2.1	General legislative barriers	21
3.2.2	Supply chain barriers	22
3.2.3	Economic barriers	22
3.2.4	Awareness and engagement barriers	22
3.2.5	Technological and design barriers	23
3.2.6	Traceability and standardization barriers	23
3.2.7	Biobased, biodegradable and compostable Products specific barriers	24
4	Screening of measures towards circular economy in plastic packaging value chain	25
4.1	Previous findings of D6.4: screening of proposed measures	25
4.1.1	Measures gathered from the analysis of legislative framework	25

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

4.1.2	Measures gathered from existing experiences.....	26
4.2	Update of the screening of proposed measures.....	26
5	Focus on End-of-Waste Criteria.....	31
6	Stakeholders consultation	41
6.1	Outcomes: Barriers	41
6.1.1	General legislative barriers	44
6.1.2	Supply chain barriers	45
6.1.3	Economic barriers	46
6.1.4	Awareness and engagement barriers	47
6.1.5	Technological and design barriers	47
6.1.6	Traceability and standardization barriers	48
6.1.7	Biobased, biodegradable and compostable products specific barriers	49
6.2	Outcomes: Measures	50
7	Policy recommendations	55
8	Conclusions.....	57
9	References.....	59
	Annex A – Policy Framework in some Member States.....	63
	Annex B – CIRCPACK Stakeholders’ Consultation	93
	Annex C – EU consultation “Future climate and energy policy - a Strategy for long-term EU greenhouse gas emissions reductions”, on behalf of Circpack	125

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

1 INTRODUCTION

This Deliverable has the overall aim to identify a set of policy recommendations for EU institutions to promote and facilitate circular economy-based schemes for plastic packaging streams, with a focus on the recycling phase.

It is embedded in Work Package 6 "Cross Sectorial Validation, Replicability and Upscaling of Solutions and specifically in Task 6.3 "Overcoming legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging". The contents of the Deliverable shall be interpreted as the direct prosecution and as complementary of the contents of D6.4, "Legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastic for packaging", which included a thorough analysis of barriers for plastic packaging recycling, consolidated through a number of interviews to appointed project partners, and a focus on the issue of end-of-waste criteria for plastic and bioplastic streams.

In detail, an overview of the existing policy framework addressing waste management and plastic packaging in particular is presented. It includes legislative updates from December 2018 at EU level and at national level for Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey. Moreover, it presents a series of factsheets to enlarge the geographical scope of the previous analysis, including a selection of Countries that were part of the European Union in 1994, when the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive was adopted in its first version. Factsheets present the major legislative instruments, overview of waste management schemes at urban and industrial level, main labels and schemes adopted.

Based on the findings of the previous activities, a set of barriers and measures is presented. Such elements fed a consultation addressed to stakeholders and published on EU Survey¹ to collect their educated opinions with this respect.

Afterwards, a focus on the theme of End of Waste² is presented in order to give a specific insight about the topic across EU as well as to investigate internal stakeholders' opinions and recommendations about the subject.

Finally, results of the survey and outputs of the other analyses performed are collected and complemented with the outcomes of stakeholders meeting held along the project. Then, the final policy recommendations are proposed.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

² https://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/framework/end_of_waste.htm

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

2 POLICY FRAMEWORK

In this Chapter, an analysis about the existing policy framework at EU level with respect to the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics is carried out. Such high level analysis aims at laying down the basis to address the bottlenecks in the overall circularity of the plastic packaging value chain and in the valorization of biobased and fossil based plastics waste as secondary raw materials.

The description of the existing policy framework at EU level starts from the results already illustrated in D6.4, which are updated in this document. This Paragraph introduces the main updates of EU policy framework in the context of fossil based plastics recycling and biobased plastics.

2.1 EU LEVEL

2.1.1 Sustainable Products in a Circular Economy - Towards an EU Product Policy Framework contributing to the Circular Economy

In its working document on Sustainable Products in a Circular Economy, the European Commission provides a synthetic overview of current initiatives towards sustainable and circular management of products in the EU.

The document identifies packaging as a priority product category for the circular economy and it summarizes the most significant ongoing actions at EU level to reduce the impacts of packaging on the environment. Specifically, it recalls the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive, the Plastics Strategy and the proposal of the Commission of new EU-wide rules to target the 10 single-use plastic products most often found on Europe's beaches and seas, including plastic bottles, food containers and wrappers as packaging products. Furthermore, sustainable Ecolabel criteria requiring packaging that is refillable and proportionate-to-its-content (e.g.: for rinse-off cosmetics or detergents) and that do not allow superfluous secondary packaging are emphasized.

2.1.2 Final Circular Economy Package and Circular Economy for Plastics

On 4 March 2019, the European Commission adopted a comprehensive report - on the implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan, already launched in 2015. The report presents the main achievements under the Action Plan and sketches out future challenges to shaping EU economy and paving the way towards a climate-neutral

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

circular economy³. Among the key documents of the Final Circular Economy Package, the report “A circular economy for plastics – Insights from research and innovation to inform policy and funding decision” adds to the Commission’s efforts towards a circular economy for plastics by strengthening the science-policy interface based on scientific evidence, collected from relevant recent projects and initiatives and it presents and elaborate their main findings. It is structured into three main parts (i.e.: impacts of plastics on society and environment; sources, designs and business models for plastics in a circular economy; circular after-use pathways for plastics) and each part deals with issues related to plastics in general, covering peculiarities for packaging and biobased products. The outcomes of the analysis include a list of policy recommendations and a cross-comparison among identified recommendations and the measures already included in “The European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy”.

2.1.3 Directive (EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment

In June 2019, the European Directive 2019/904 on Single Use Plastics entered in force, after having been adopted by the Council in May. EU rules on single-use plastic products, target the 10 plastic items that most often pollute Europe’s beaches and seas, along with lost or abandoned fishing gear. This waste accounts for 70 % of marine litter. The rules ban single-use disposable plastic products for which plastic-free alternatives already exist. Other measures aim to reduce the consumption of the most frequently littered plastic products; to extend the producers’ responsibility; to change the design of some products; and to inform and raise awareness among consumers.

From 2021 a ban will be in place for single-use plastic cotton bud sticks, cutlery, plates, straws, drink stirrers and balloon sticks, as well as food and beverage containers – including cups – made of expanded polystyrene. These items will all have to be made from more sustainable materials or replaced with reusable alternatives. All products made of oxo-degradable plastics will also be banned.

Replacing the most common single-use plastic items with multiple-use or better-designed products can lead to innovative solutions and new business models. For example, reuse programmes can replace many of the single-use plastic products, and use of alternative materials could reinforce the EU’s lead in the bioeconomy⁴.

The contents of the Regulation are expected to be enforced by the Member States within July 2021.

³ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

⁴ <https://www.bereadytochange.eu/en/>

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

2.1.4 The European Green Deal

The European Green Deal is the roadmap for making the EU's economy sustainable. This will happen by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities across all policy areas and making the transition just and inclusive.

This strategy has been set out by the European Commission in December 2019 and it tackles the climate and environmental related challenges across all the sectors. Currently, the Proposal for a Regulation establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality is under assessment.

The strategy foresees the development of requirements to ensure that "all packaging in the EU market is reusable or recyclable in an economically viable manner by 2030, will develop a regulatory framework for biodegradable and bio-based plastics, and will implement measures on single use plastics". Moreover, it states that the Commission will consider legal requirements to boost the market of secondary raw materials with mandatory recycled content, also for packaging materials.

As a key action suggested in the Strategy, a New Circular Economy Action Plan has been launched and the updated plan has been published in 2020. This Circular Economy Action Plan provides a future-oriented agenda for achieving a cleaner and more competitive Europe in co-creation with economic actors, consumers, citizens and civil society organisations. It specifically promotes:

- waste reduction targets for specific streams and other measures on waste prevention (expected in 2022);
- EU-wide harmonized model for separate collection of waste and labelling to facilitate separate collection (expected in 2022);
- scoping the development of further EU-wide end-of-waste and by-product criteria (expected in 2021);
- updating the Circular Economy Monitoring Framework to reflect new policy priorities and develop further indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints (expected 2021).

For the packaging sector, the Commission plans to review the Directive 94/62/EC "to reinforce the mandatory essential requirements for packaging to be allowed on the EU market"; for this scope, the Commission will focus on reducing (over)packaging and packaging waste, driving design for re-use and recyclability of packaging, considering reducing the complexity of packaging materials. For the sector of plastic products, the Plan foresees the proposal of "mandatory requirements for recycled content and waste reduction measures for key products such as packaging, construction materials and vehicles". Moreover – among other initiatives - it boosts the development of labels, standardization and certification measures.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

2.2 NATIONAL LEVEL

This section includes an overview of the national legislative frameworks of major Countries within the EU concerning, plastic packaging and circular economy. The analysis – as a continuation of D6.4 - aims at providing an overview of the high-level legislative opportunities aiming at supporting the recycle and recovery of plastic packaging. The Countries included in the analysis are a selection of Countries that were part of the European Union in 1994, when the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive was adopted in its first version. As such, they often present advanced levels of development of measure to boost circular economy in this sector. Country by country, each paragraph describes the major legislative instruments and includes information about operators of waste management at urban and industrial level, as well as main labels and schemes adopted at national level. This information feeds the identification of subsequent barriers and measures, for the development of policy recommendations.

2.2.1 Updates from D6.3

2.2.1.1 Italy

In May 2019, EoW criteria for absorbent hygiene products were adopted, aiming at increasing recovery rates for such items and at generating increasing value in the respective value chain. In addition, activities for the definition of EoW criteria for tires, paper and cardboard, mixed plastics and construction&demolition waste are ongoing.

In November 2019, Decree 101/2019 entered in force and it gave permission to regional authorities to release case-by-case EoW authorizations. Such authorizations may be checked and controlled by the National authority.

In December 2019, the Decree 27/12/2019 n°160 “Legge di Bilancio 2020” entered in force. Among the measures addressed by the decree, a plastic tax on single use plastic containers is introduced. The tax – to be paid by the manufacturers of single use packaging products - amounts of 0.45 €/kg of plastic, and compostable products are exempted from the tax. However, this measure has still not yet been implemented, to allow some months for potential technological changes to the set up of the enterprises that will be affected by the tax.

Next activities in the field of end-of-waste legislation concern the adoption of end-of-waste criteria for waste paper.

2.2.1.2 Spain

No major legislative updates are found in Spain.

In July 2019, a proposal for the reduction of single use plastics was published in the “Boletín Oficial de las Cortes Generales”, even though at the moment concrete action has not yet been taken.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

In February 2020, in a “Nota de Prensa”, the Government confirms it is planning to introduce a plastic tax for single use packaging.

In addition, the strategy for a circular economy is currently under development.

2.2.1.3 Croatia

From January 2019, the Article 14a of Ordinance on packaging and waste packaging published on November 2017, entered into force. All lightweight plastic carrying bags (fossil-based and biobased with a wall thickness of less than 50 microns) are charged to the consumers at the point of sale of goods or products. Very lightweight plastic carrying bags with a wall thickness of less than 15 microns which are used "exclusively" for high reasons or which serve exclusively as primary packaging for food are free given at the point of sale but with notice to the consumers about energy-saving and rational use of these bags by labelling content " BAGS-USE FRUGALLY".

In January 2020, an amendment to the Rules on of packaging and packaging waste was signed by the Ministry of Energy and Environment. The amendment is aimed at facilitating the achievements of the target for packaging waste management. Main changes include the introduction of packaging for milky and dairy products into the existing national deposit refund systems as well as a reduction for sorting costs for public services collecting mixed and biodegradable municipal waste who participates in the packaging waste collection system, based on the amount of waste collected. Such reduction may also be agreed in case the sorted waste is exported, upon approval.

Also, in January 2020, an amendment to the Act of Sustainable waste Management entered into force, including provisions about the supervision of public services for collection of mixed municipal waste and collection of biodegradable municipal waste, to be enforced by the competent administrative body of the county dedicated to waste management.

In addition, it is highlighted that the Industrial Strategy of the Republic of Croatia 2014–2020, the Strategy for Innovation Encouragement of the Republic of Croatia 2014–2020 and especially the National Action Plan for Green Public Procurement for the period 2015–2017 with the view till 2020, based on the principles of circular economy are approaching their conclusion, possibly leaving space for introduction of new strategies in the field of circular economy.

2.2.1.4 Turkey

In December 2018, Amending Law on the Environmental Law and Some Laws which foresees a ban on free plastic bags entered into force. In Procedures and Principles Regarding Pricing of Plastic Bags entered into force in January 2019 and was revised in March 2019. All lightweight plastic carrying bags (fossil-based and biobased) with a wall thickness of more than 40 microns are charged to the consumers at the point of sale of goods or products with barcode and notice to the consumers about environmental protection and zero waste logo, while very lightweight plastic carrying bags with wall thickness less than 15 microns in sales markets, pharmacies or as primary packaging for

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

food are given free of charge at the point of sale since 1 January 2019. The target is reducing plastic carrying bag consumption per capita from 440 to 90 until 31 December 2019 and to 40 until 31 December 2025.

Zero Waste Regulation came into force in July 2019. With the regulation, separate collection of plastic waste at source and requirements about this subject are stated. Zero Waste System is a 7-step roadmap consisting of steps that companies, institutions or organizations should apply to be included in Zero Waste starting in 2020, forcing to establish and approve the zero waste license, targeting to prevent and reduce the amount of waste.

Moreover, the actual allowed plastic materials are given in Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on Food Contact Plastic Materials and Articles published in December 2019.

In March 2020, a change was made in the Regulation on Control of Packaging Waste in order to adopt Zero Waste System. With the amendment, recovery and recycling targets of packaging waste have been updated and the liabilities of parties have changed

2.2.2 Overview across Member States

Each section below summarizes the main findings of a Country-specific analysis. In order to improve the usability of this document, the details for each single Member States are reported in Annex A.

Main Policy Framework

Each Member State presents different legislative instruments with respect to waste management in general and plastic packaging waste in detail. Overall, clearly the national legislations well reflect the provisions of the European Directives.

Moreover, it is common that Countries develop strategic initiatives and action plans in the fields of bioeconomy, resource efficiency and circular economy. Such instruments act as drivers for the improvement also of the national performance with respect to waste management.

As far as specific legislation for plastic packaging is concerned, each Country presents different peculiarities. Examples of measures addressed the consumption of shopping bags (Austria, Belgium, Finland, Ireland, Sweden), requirements about recycled contents (Belgium, France, The Netherlands), bans on single use plastic (Denmark, France) implementation of deposit/return systems (Denmark), EPR schemes (France), recycling targets (Germany), packaging tax (Finland) and green public procurement (Ireland, Portugal).

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

Each Member State presents specific waste management models, for both urban packaging waste or commercial and industrial packaging waste. This situation implies

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

that different actors are involved in the waste management value chain, depending on the Country.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 show management models and responsibility schemes in place for urban waste in the MSs for prevention, collection and recycle and recovery respectively.

Table 1. Management model and responsibility scheme for urban waste in some Member States (Prevention)

Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (Producers)	Deposit system for reuse	Member States
X			Austria, Spain, France, The Netherlands, Belgium, Greece, Luxembourg, Ireland
	X		Germany
X		X	Portugal, Sweden, Finland, Denmark

Table 2. Management model and responsibility scheme for urban waste in some Member States (Collection)

Local authorities	EPR systems	Tax scheme	Deposit system for recycle	Member States
X				France, Portugal, Belgium, Luxembourg, Ireland
	X			Austria
	X	X	X	Germany, Sweden
X	X			Greece, Spain
X			X	The Netherlands, Denmark
	X	X	X	Finland

Table 3. Management model and responsibility scheme for urban waste in some Member States (Recycle and recovery)

Local authorities	EPR systems	Tax scheme	Deposit system for recycle	Member States
	X			Austria, Portugal, Spain, France, Belgium, Luxembourg, Ireland, Greece
	X		X	Germany, The Netherlands, Sweden
X			X	Denmark
	X	X	X	Finland

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6 show management models and responsibility schemes in place for commercial and industrial waste in the MSs for prevention, collection and recycle and recovery respectively.

Table 4. Management model and responsibility scheme for commercial and industrial waste in some Member States (Prevention)

Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (Producers)	Deposit system for reuse	Member States
X			Austria, Spain, France, Finland, The Netherlands, Sweden, Belgium, Greece, Luxembourg, Ireland, Denmark
	X		Germany
X		X	Portugal

Table 5. Management model and responsibility scheme for commercial and industrial waste in some Member States (Collection)

Local authorities	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators	EPR systems	Member States
	X	X	Austria, Greece, Luxembourg
	X		Denmark, France, Germany, Portugal, Spain
		X	Belgium, Finland, The Netherlands, Sweden
X			Ireland

Table 6. Management model and responsibility scheme for commercial and industrial waste in some Member States (Recycle and recovery)

Local authorities	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators	EPR systems	Member States
	X	X	Austria, Greece, Luxembourg
	X		Denmark, France, Germany, Portugal, Spain
		X	Belgium, Finland, Ireland, Sweden

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

The theme of business compliance is faced quite homogeneously across MSs, in terms of instruments available to standardize waste management and production.

As far as the control of environmental impacts is concerned, conformity to a series of international standards (EN 13427, EN 13428, EN 13429, EN 13430, EN 13431, EN 13432) is desired for packaging waste.

Moreover, in each MS one or more producer responsibility organizations are present to properly manage the waste collection, sorting and treatment. Depending on the specific type of packaging and its end-use, importers and/or producers shall be compliant to the organization, by paying a fee for the collection, sorting and treatment of the packaging at its end of life. In some MSs, specific schemes and fees are foreseen for plastic bottles and beverage containers (e.g.: Germany).

Self-compliance and independent waste management is accepted in some cases for commercial and industrial waste (e.g.: Greece).

Labelling

In all the analyzed MSs, the labeling is compliant with Decision 129/97/CE "Establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE".

The green dot label is widely used, as the producer responsibility organizations are usually accredited systems to use the label.

Penalties

In all the analyzed MSs, penalties are in place to enforce companies to subscribe to the required waste management systems and to limit improper use of labels.

3 BARRIERS TO CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN PLASTIC PACKAGING VALUE CHAIN

3.1 PREVIOUS FINDINGS OF D6.4

Below, the list of barriers resulting from the work performed until M18 is reported. Such barriers result from a desk analysis phase, consolidated through interviews to project partners and analysis of different national contexts:

- existence of technological gap between the MS in collection, selection, treating and processing of plastic packaging waste (e.g. Croatia buy plastic waste from other countries where collection is better segregated, or buy production waste, which does not require as much energy and water as reprocessing post-consumer waste);

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

- no efforts to find “definitive” EoW Criteria for plastics (regulation), but instead to provide guidelines for MS in the management of the “no longer waste” materials;
- existence criticisms related to the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislations;
- doubts about the future implementation of the proposal for Directive, “on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment,” the European Commission has come up with measures banning or restricting the use of single-use plastic application (such as plates, cutlery, cups, plastic bags, etc.) including biodegradable & compostable plastics;
- biodegradable & compostable plastics are designed to be organically recycled and banning products such as plates, cutlery, or cups, which are used efficiently especially in collective catering, would only block further research & development in this sector;
- difficulties in the organic waste stream selection caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics;
- need of high quality standards of compost, that requires refining interventions,
- high effort invested, and high costs related to the disposal of the huge quantities of waste produced;
- packaging wastes are not always collected separately and legally (e.g. in Turkey);
- since recycled plastics may do not have the same quality and performance compared to virgin plastics, this can be a technical barrier becoming a challenge for future technological developments e.g. monitoring systems.

3.2 UPDATE OF BARRIERS

This paragraph is intended to enlarge the findings of D6.4 by providing additional barriers as outcome of a wide literature review, including reference to European and National Policy frameworks. The selected barriers are presented according to the following categories: general barriers, economic barriers, barriers concerning awareness and engagement issues, barriers concerning technological and design issues, barriers concerning traceability and standardization and finally barriers specific for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastic streams. For each category, a brief explanation about the relevance of the category towards the case of circular economy for plastic packaging products is provided and then, the specific list of barriers is reported.

3.2.1 General legislative barriers

This category includes the barriers that cannot be directly addressed to more specific categories and that are strongly related with policy framework.

List of barriers:

- absence of End of Waste criteria for plastic packaging waste;

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

- use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer;
- possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation;
- landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries;
- difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials;
- poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging.

3.2.2 Supply chain barriers

This category includes the barriers that affect the circularity of the plastic packaging value chain because of unbalanced mechanisms along the entire value chain.

List of barriers:

- existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging;
- inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers;
- low capillarity of re-processing plants and logistic issues (e.g.: if only a limited number of re-processing plants exist, difficulties and increased costs for waste to be converted may arise).

3.2.3 Economic barriers

Economic factors play a crucial role in determining the success of innovative value chains, as it is highly likely that schemes that generate economic benefits/savings will be adopted by the key actors along the value chain.

List of barriers:

- lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practices such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice;
- the cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues;
- lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging;
- material incineration – as a form of down-cycling of plastic packaging – can be cheaper than recycling.

3.2.4 Awareness and engagement barriers

Considering the massive volume of plastic packaging products in numerous industrial segments and in citizens daily activities, high level of engagement of all the parties and

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

effective education towards a correct management of these products can generate also in the short term a positive impacts on the performance of existing and innovative value chains.

List of barriers:

- lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of improved plastic waste management;
- lack of citizens education about correct waste management.

3.2.5 Technological and design barriers

Design practice and available technologies influence the efficiency of a circular value chain. For instance, a different design can guarantee the reusability or recyclability of a certain packaging product, while available technology can enable an efficient sorting process and enhance the outcome of a recycling process.

Currently, complicated packaging designs exist, with commonly little regard for end-of-life sorting and recycling. Plastic packaging is often made from one or more different polymers, depending on its purpose, in order to combine functional properties to meet production and use requirements. In some other cases, such complexity is solely marketing and brand driven (e.g. black trays for meat and ready meals; gloss finishes; pack clarity for beverages). In addition, recycling is often hampered by the lack of technological solutions either for certain polymers, products or by the lack of an insufficient quality of the secondary raw material.

List of barriers:

- the variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products) is not reflected in the variety of technologies for sorting and recycling;
- many recycling processes are still not optimal, leading to a loss in material quality and quantity;
- nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process;
- a sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products.

3.2.6 Traceability and standardization barriers

In circular schemes, where many players benefit from the same product/material along its life, the need of transparency about the quality of the product is essential to facilitate its spread in multiple sectors.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

List of barriers:

- incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detail information about the secondary raw material;
- fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion;
- low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design.

3.2.7 Biobased, biodegradable and compostable Products specific barriers

The use of biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastic packaging products is quite recent and constitutes only a niche sector in comparison with the traditional plastic sector, centred on fossil sources and disposal / incineration / recycle end-of-life. Thus, these products and materials present some peculiar features that cannot be embedded in the case of traditional plastic.

List of barriers:

- the definition of "bioplastic" includes a variety of different materials, with distinct implications regarding its origin and respective End-of-Life options, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both;
- difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics and by the lack of efficient separate collection of bio-waste in all MSs;
- lack of composting facilities able to treat all types of bio-waste (as defined by WFD) and to produce high quality content.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

4 SCREENING OF MEASURES TOWARDS CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN PLASTIC PACKAGING VALUE CHAIN

4.1 PREVIOUS FINDINGS OF D6.4: SCREENING OF PROPOSED MEASURES

Below, the list of measures to overcome existing barriers resulting from the work performed until M18 is reported. Such measures result from a desk analysis phase, consolidated through interviews to project partners and analysis of different national contexts and are subdivided into measures gathered from the analysis of legislative framework and measures gathered from existing experiences.

4.1.1 Measures gathered from the analysis of legislative framework

- as an alternative and complementary action to EoW Criteria, the European Commission is promoting bilateral agreements between MSs;
- existing EoW criteria established between specific MSs (i.e.: not implemented as regulation at European level) can be used as basis to draft other similar agreements, also for non-EU countries;
- private entities can benefit from specific EoW criteria, but with the support of the public entities that have the duty to assist and legitimise them;
- standardization should be promoted in order to increase the traceability of recycled materials, considering that the secondary raw materials market is growing;
- EoW Criteria oriented towards specific targeted applications including the replacement of fossil feedstocks with compostable bioplastics should be adopted;
- national and municipal legislative frameworks should foster the improvement of the quality of recycling, for example through improvement of separate collection schemes;
- a clear and stable policy framework, including the creation of clear quality standards and demand support measures, as well as incentives for research, innovation, and training should be created in order to promote investments;
- legislative actions aimed at fostering the emergence and limiting the costs of environmental externalities should be designed, as well as for the promotion of the economy circularity through the application of specific fiscal measures and the simplification of the rules governing waste recover;
- promotion of law enforcement of already existing legislation, concrete adoption of green public procurement, creation of flagship project for specific supply chain case studies and diffusion of private-public partnerships should be promoted.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

4.1.2 Measures gathered from existing experiences

- Technical obstacles related to performances, quality, reliability and proper separation methods can be helped by holistic legislative framework;
- raise citizens awareness on the topic of sustainability, through specific education schemes aimed at conveying the importance and the need of virtuous practices, and through public campaigns;
- proper communication about the difference between plastic and compostable bioplastics should be promoted, as it is crucial to assure collection of compostable plastics into the organic waste streams;
- promotion for the consumers about potential benefits of biobased packaging materials should be increased, in order to facilitate the shift from fossil feedstock to biological resources when it is beneficial;
- cooperation between private and public entities of different MSs should be improved, as it can be an effective opportunity to fill technological gaps between MSs and an opportunity for all MSs to reach the EU targets jointly;
- sharing of the legislative experiences among the MS can support the development of national legislative frameworks with common characteristics, in order to avoid regulatory barriers due to fragmentation and to facilitate international trades.

4.2 UPDATE OF THE SCREENING OF PROPOSED MEASURES

This paragraph is intended to enlarge the findings of D6.4 by providing additional measures to overcome existing barriers as outcome of the analysis of the existing legislative framework and of a wide literature review. The selected measures are intended to address the clusters of barriers previously presented.

In general terms, **fiscal tools**, both at the national and regional level, can represent economic deterrents to practices (e.g.: unsustainable plastic packaging products and inefficient waste management schemes).

Economic deterrents are relevant because plastic packaging products and waste – especially if not correctly managed – are responsible for negative impacts in terms of degradation of natural systems due to leakage, impacts on land use, biodiversity and air quality, greenhouse gas emissions. These impacts are usually correlated to the primary feedstock used for packaging production. A number of economic schemes aimed at incorporating such externalities into the full cost of end-products already exist, with the final aim of increasing recovery rates. In addition, the EU legislation sets out an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Scheme for end-of-life vehicles, batteries and accumulators as well as waste electrical and electronic good waste streams. EPR involves a shift in responsibility in the treatment of waste from the public authorities to manufacturers that are in charge of the treatment and disposal cost of the waste generated by their products. However, only few collective EPR schemes have developed mechanisms to lower the fees for eco-designed products and ensure that producer fees incentivize

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

prevention, reparability and recyclability. In addition, also an increase of taxation for non-desired management routes for PPW can play as a deterrent. Indeed, countries with landfill restrictions of recyclable and recoverable waste have, on average, higher recycling rates of plastic post-consumer waste.

On the other hand, economic incentives and rewards can promote desired circular schemes in the industrial sector and can incentivize also individual consumers towards a more conscious use and disposal of plastic packaging products. They can enhance the sorting efficiency, the investments in new technologies and boost development in design practice, which will improve the quantity and quality of recycled plastics. Such incentives can be implemented, for example, as tax reduction, fee reduction, funds, facilitated loans, etc.

Outside the economic solutions, the **encouragement of a wide stakeholder group**, including designers - that play a critical role along the entire product value chain - **and policymakers**, who can trigger progress in the near term, is important to generate a system shift to circular economy in the plastic packaging sector. Numerous studies have also highlighted the lack of full harmonisation of collection and recovery systems for packaging as a relevant concern for the implementation of circular value chains for packaging products in the EU.

Moreover, **awareness raising** initiatives are a consolidated instrument to spread knowledge about the challenges of the plastics economy and on how to address them along the entire value chains. These initiatives may play a crucial role especially in educating citizens, which play a key role in the collection and sorting of plastic packaging waste and municipal waste in general. Indeed, packaging waste is often varied in composition, may be multi-material and contaminated with other materials (e.g. organics). This complicates material sorting, resulting in mixed packaging streams being collected, often with high levels of contamination, both in terms of “non-target” polymers and contamination with other materials.

As an intermediate solution to the lack of awareness and lack of economic incentives, **Green Public Procurement** is a voluntary instrument that acts as driver and financial incentive, generating an important contribution to sustainable consumption and production. As a matter of fact, the economic significance of public procurement in Europe is considerable, involving around 14% of GDP in the EU on the purchase of services, works and supplies. As such, its use should not be restricted to the public sector and should be also considered by private companies, especially the large ones, which can enforce a significant influence on multiple industrial segments.

From a **technological and design perspective**, main measures should face the fact that at current stage, a wide variety of complex packaging designs exist, with commonly little regard for end-of-life sorting and recycling. In order to facilitate the end-of-life management, the recycling and recovery processes, plastic packaging manufacturers should increase their efforts towards more end-of-life oriented design approaches. In such context, the current Ecodesign Directive (2009/125/EC) aims to make new products

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

more energy efficient. In 2018, the European Parliament has called to go beyond energy efficiency and consider other aspects in the design of new products, such as how long a product lasts, how easy it is to take apart, repair and recycle. More in detail, Annex II of Directive 94/62/EC on Packaging and Packaging Waste includes a list of Essential Requirements on the composition and the reusable and recoverable, including recyclable, nature of packaging. However, criteria have been recently discussed as they may be too loose to guarantee effective implementation of eco-design principles, which are difficult to enforce.

Criteria include, e.g.:

- “Packaging shall be so manufactured that the packaging volume and weight be limited to the minimum adequate amount to maintain the necessary level of safety, hygiene and acceptance for the packed product and for the consumer”;
- “Packaging shall be designed, produced and commercialized in such a way as to permit its reuse or recovery, including recycling, and to minimize its impact on the environment when packaging waste or residues from packaging waste management operations are disposed of”.

A continuous development of reprocessing technologies to enable the recycling of materials that cannot be processed into high-quality products today and a continuous improvement of the quality of secondary raw material to allow for more subsequent loops in the product value chain are desirable. Besides, also an increase in the efficiency of the sorting process of municipal waste can be considered as a technological improvement, as logistic factors and must be considered when local and regional authorities decide to improve separate collection systems of plastic waste, as well as size and density of population in the geographical area concerned and related socioeconomic conditions.

A prerequisite for increased performance and investments in the recycling chain is the existence of a demand capable of absorbing the outputs of the recycling facilities. However, it happens that secondary raw material is not absorbed because it does not meet the requirements of the manufacturing industry. One possibility to overcome this situation is often associated with EoW criteria. Indeed, the purpose of end-of-waste criteria is to avoid confusion about the waste definition and to clarify when certain waste that has undergone recovery ceases to be waste. Recycling should be supported by creating legal certainty and an equal level playing field and by removing unnecessary administrative burdens. For the same purpose, in order to build a change in the perception of quality and performance of products manufactured from recycled materials, labels may be used a support for this cultural shift, by communicating recycled content, possible end-of-life routes, etc.

Lastly, the development of **biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastic** shall be addressed. Today's plastics industry is defined by a fossil-based feedstock and energy paradigm, structured in a well consolidated and long standing scheme. Thus, despite many efforts at European, national and local level, scale-up and commercialisation of

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

bio-based feedstock or completely novel (plastic) materials remains rather limited. Improvements to guarantee clear distinction between bioplastics products and conventional plastic products, transparent marketing communication, homogenised labels are among the most urgent issues in this specific stream of bioplastic and biodegradable/compostable products.

List of measures:

- encourage collaboration between Member States, in order to align their approach and narrow the existing gaps as much as possible;
- guarantee use of a homogeneous terminology with respect to waste and waste management across different policies and different sectors;
- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling);
- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content;
- incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria;
- a sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products;
- reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions;
- introduce incentives to guarantee that the most sustainable recycling routes are cost-effective compared with the other available options (e.g.: incineration);
- launch the establishment of waste management tariff schemes based on the amount of waste actually produced and on the quality of sorting achieved;
- promote eco-designed packaging solutions and waste prevention in packaging design within the EPR schemes, for example by introducing quantitative targets on such performances;
- introduce landfill bans or increase landfill costs in order to make recycle more cost effective and – in parallel – introduce incentives or tax exemptions to decrease the cost of recycle of certain plastic streams;
- facilitate negotiating mechanisms for trade agreements that allow to increase recovery rates, to reduce recovery tariffs and to accelerate materials import and export;
- boost networking initiatives for industrial stakeholders committed to the achievement of a circular and sustainable economy for plastic packaging and their connection with other industrial sectors;
- increase consumers' awareness about packaging design, properties and values through standardized labels, including on products precise statements about the presence of multi-material packaging, separable packaging parts, biobased material;

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

- increase consumers' awareness about the importance of implementing virtuous waste management practices and increase guidance on sorting procedures available in their area, in order to increase the level of separation and to increase the overall quality and efficiency of the recycling process;
- promote design best practices and guidelines across the plastic packaging manufacturing industry;
- introduce more stringent Essential Requirements for packaging products to be put on the market and establish control schemes to ensure compliance of products with such requirements;
- encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies;
- promote research to structure the most effective waste management system (e.g.: collection, sorting at plant, sorting at consumers) in relation with citizens' awareness level, urban geographical context, available technologies, etc.;
- increase transparency in waste traceability, by encouraging municipalities or entities responsible for waste management to create robust datasets for each waste streams and by introducing certificates of waste treatments performed and source of waste material;
- introduce minimum requirements for secondary raw material specifications and labels;
- define EoW for fossil plastic waste streams;
- define EoW for bio-plastic waste streams;
- promote environmental labels and product declaration for packaging product, covering the entire life cycle;
- promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials;
- ban certain traditional fossil-based plastic products and – in parallel – facilitate the commercialization of innovative equivalent bio-based compostable products;
- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

5 FOCUS ON END-OF-WASTE CRITERIA

The need of introducing the concept of End of Waste arises from the principle of circular economy according to which waste shall be reintroduced into the economy as products and secondary raw materials.

Thus, the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC, as amended in 2018, describes the conditions to define criteria that waste should meet to enter the end-of-waste status, ceasing to be waste and becoming a secondary product. The conditions, outlined in Article 6(1) are:

- (a) the substance or object is to be used for specific purposes;
- (b) a market or demand exists for such a substance or object;
- (c) the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products;
- (d) the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

Since the introduction of the concept of EoW criteria, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has worked on the development of technical reports addressing the issue of EoW for a selection of material flows. Among the technical proposals received, the Commission has so far adopted the following Regulations laying down EU wide EoW criteria:

- iron, steel and aluminium scrap (Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011);
- glass cullet (Commission Regulation (EU) N° 1179/2012);
- copper scrap (Commission Regulation (EU) N° 715/2013).

Among the JRC Technical reports, there are also and End-of-waste criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate) and “End-of-waste criteria for waste plastic for conversion”. Nevertheless, these proposals have not been adopted in the EU regulatory framework, possibly due to difficulties in reaching agreements across all MSs, considering the different needs and priorities of each Country.

In detail, the European Strategy for Circular Economy states that “for plastic waste, the European Commission carried out a review, but end-of waste criteria have not been set because of the complexity and diversity of polymers and variety of potential applications. There would be a merit to provide businesses with harmonised quality standards for recycling practices and for recyclates in order to provide supportive business environment. Moreover, none of the existing standards and technical specifications fits the purpose of end-of-waste criteria and only business to business specifications define in practice the technical characteristics of waste plastics and recyclates.”

Some MSs have also developed a national legislative framework for the development of national EoW criteria, as encouraged by the Waste Framework Directive itself. As a result,

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

the framework for the development of EoW criteria is evolving in a fragmented way, depending on each MS and this lack of harmonisation on end-of-waste criteria is sometimes considered to hinder a free waste market. National end-of-waste criteria can lead to uncertainties for waste operators and reduce their ability to exchange on best practices between their different entities.

Table 7 below shows a few examples of EoW legislation in MSs at national or regional level, as derived from the TRIS database⁵. However, a database of case-by-case accepted EoW criteria is not available at EU level, due to the fact that these publications do not fall under any reporting obligation.

Table 7. EoW in certain Member States.

Member State	Details on EoW legislation
Belgium	Wallonia adopted EoW criteria for paper and aggregates (28/2/2019 - Decree of Walloon Government setting out the procedures for implementing Article 4ter of the Decree of 27 June 1996 on waste concerning the end-of-waste procedure)
Estonia	Estonia adopted EoW criteria for biogas digestate generated from biodegradable waste (Regulation No 12 of the Minister for the Environment of 10 May 2016)
France	France adopted EoW criteria for used-oil distillation residues (Arrêté du 10 juillet 2017 fixant les critères de sortie du statut de déchet pour les résidus de distillation des huiles usagées pour un usage comme plastifiant de bitumes dans la fabrication de membranes d'étanchéité pour toiture), waste from animal fat, used cooking oil and biofuels made therefrom (Arrêté du 24 août 2016 fixant les critères de sortie du statut de déchet pour les déchets gras et les huiles alimentaires usagées pour un usage en tant que combustible dans une installation de combustion classée sous la rubrique 2910-B au titre de la nomenclature des installations classées pour la protection de l'environnement et d'une puissance supérieure à 0,1 MW et les esters méthyliques d'acides gras fabriqués à partir de ces déchets destinés à être incorporés dans un produit pétrolier), items and chemicals that have been prepared for reuse (Arrêté du 11 décembre 2018 fixant les critères de sortie du statut de déchet pour les objets et produits chimiques ayant fait l'objet d'une préparation en vue de la reutilisation), cut wiping cloths made from used textiles (Arrêté du 25 février 2019 fixant les critères de sortie du statut de déchet pour les chiffons d'essuyage coupés élaborés à partir de textiles usagés pour un usage comme chiffons), chemical products or items that have undergone a process of regeneration (Arrêté du 22 février 2019 fixant les critères de sortie du statut de déchet pour les produits chimiques ou objets ayant fait l'objet d'une régénération)

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/tris/en/>

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Member State	Details on EoW legislation
Italy	Italy adopted EoW criteria for solid recovered fuel (DECRETO 14 febbraio 2013, n. 22. Regolamento recante disciplina della cessazione della qualifica di rifiuti di determinate tipologie di combustibili solidi secondari (CSS), ai sensi dell'articolo 184-ter, comma 2, del decreto legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152, e successive modificazioni.), vulcanised rubber (Decreto del Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare 19 Novembre 2019, n° 182), bituminous concrete (DECRETO 28 marzo 2018, n. 69 Regolamento recante disciplina della cessazione della qualifica di rifiuto di conglomerato bituminoso ai sensi dell'articolo 184-ter, comma 2 del decreto legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152), absorbent hygiene products (Decreto 15 maggio 2019, n. 62. Regolamento recante disciplina della cessazione della qualifica di rifiuto da prodotti assorbenti per la persona (PAP), ai sensi dell'articolo 184-ter, comma 2, del decreto legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152.)
Portugal	Portugal adopted EoW criteria for rubber materials from used tyres (Ordinance No. 20/2018, Diário da República no. 12/2018, Series I of 2018-01-17, Estabelece os critérios para a atribuição do Fim do Estatuto de Resíduo (FER) ao material de borracha derivado de pneus usados) and recovered plastic (Portaria n.º 245/2017, Diário da República n.º 148/2017, Série I de 2017-08-02, Estabelece os critérios para a atribuição do Fim do Estatuto de Resíduo (FER) ao plástico recuperado).
Spain	Spain adopted EoW criteria for processed oil (Orden APM/205/2018, de 22 de febrero, por la que se establecen los criterios para determinar cuándo el aceite usado procesado procedente del tratamiento de aceites usados para su uso como combustible deja de ser residuo con arreglo a la Ley 22/2011, de 28 de julio, de residuos y suelos contaminados), fuel recovered from the treatment of type C MARPOL (Orden APM/206/2018, de 22 de febrero, por la que se establecen los criterios para determinar cuándo el fuel recuperado procedente del tratamiento de residuos MARPOL tipo c para su uso como combustible en buques deja de ser residuo con arreglo a la Ley 22/2011, de 28 de julio, de residuos y suelos contaminados). In addition, work for adoption of EoW criteria for paper and cardboard is ongoing (Proyecto de Orden por la que se establecen los criterios para determinar cuándo el papel y cartón para reciclar deja de ser residuo con arreglo a la Ley 22/2011, de 28 de julio, de residuos y suelos contaminados) Basque Countries adopted EoW criteria for aggregates (ORDEN de 12 de enero de 2015, de la Consejera de Medio Ambiente y Política Territorial por la que se establecen los requisitos para la utilización de los áridos reciclados procedentes de la valorización de residuos de construcción y demolición).
The Netherlands	The Netherlands adopted EoW criteria for granulate (Regeling van de Staatssecretaris van Infrastructuur en Milieu, van 5 februari 2015, nr. IENM/BSK-2015/18222, houdende vaststelling van regels ter bepaling van de status einde-afval van recyclinggranulaat (Regeling vaststelling van de status einde-afval van recyclinggranulaat).

From the analysis it results that the only MS that adopted an EoW criteria for general plastic waste is Portugal.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

In detail, the Portuguese Decree applies to streams of scales, agglomerates and granules plastic waste, allowing its incorporation as a secondary raw material in the production processes. The criteria that recovered plastic shall comply when transferred from the producer to a subsequent actor include: a set of technical criteria, clearly based on the proposal of the JRC for the drafting of EoW criteria for recovered plastic, a set of criteria about labelling and management of the recovered waste and – finally – a set of criteria referred to the future use of recovered plastic.

Moreover, depending on the National legislation, where criteria have not been set at either Union or national level a MS may decide on a case-by-case basis, or take appropriate measures to verify, that certain waste has ceased to be waste. Therefore, where no EU EoW criteria are defined, Member States may fall into one of following cases with respect to EoW criteria development:

- only national end-of-waste criteria are used. No case-by-case decisions;
- only case-by-case decisions. No national end-of-waste criteria apply;
- a mix of national end-of-waste criteria and case-by-case decisions.

Currently, Countries located in Northern Europe (e.g.: The Netherlands, Sweden) are usually more inclined to leave more responsibility to the operators, on a case by case basis. Conversely, Countries such as Spain and France have a centralized model for the development of EoW, occurring at national level.

However, when a case-by-case decision needs to be made regarding the end-of waste status of a recovered material, regulators and businesses often experience barriers and uncertainties, for example for the determination and validation of the technical EoW criteria.

Detailed feedback was collected among the partners in order to gain a deep understanding of the role of end-of-waste in business as usual, as well as potential improvement of the criteria to unlock the recyclability. In addition to the findings already highlighted in D6.3, updated and precise insights are proposed.

For the case of fossil-plastic, it results that the EoW criteria are not seen as directly related to the recycling step of the value chain, but they are rather enablers and guarantee of the economic and environmental sustainability and feasibility of the entire value chain. As concrete examples, they enlarge the spectrum of companies with which commercial exchanges are possible (e.g.: in Italy, only few companies are allowed to receive as input waste materials) and facilitate many operations needed across the value chain in general, preventing that the products fall under the requirements of waste legislation.

Of course the validation of the technology is the step that practically enables the recycling process, but still the EoW criteria is the scheme that enhances the possibilities and the up-scaling of a circular value chain, making it competitive as secondary raw material in the market, also with respect to virgin raw materials. Eventually, the economic feasibility plays a crucial role in the success of the value chains and often it is coupled with environmental performance of the product.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

The fragmentation of EoW criteria adoption existing at EU level stands as a barrier to the security and reliability of the market across the different MSs, in those situations in which different EoW criteria are adopted for the same waste flow or in which a flow is subject to EoW legislation in one country but not in another. There is broad consensus that the adoption of EoW criteria for plastic and biomaterials should be pursued especially at EU level. However, the technical proposal from JRC, or other proposals, have never been actually adopted by the European Commission and according to information collected during CIRCPACK project there is no intention to follow this path for plastics or plastics-related flows.

A homogeneous coverage would increase confidence in import and export of secondary raw materials, as well as increase the volume of converted waste.

A possible way through this fragmentation the EU is to screen existing EoW criteria across Members States and evaluate their homogeneous adoption. This would reduce the efforts of the Commission in developing technical proposals for the criteria on one hand, but it will still improve the regulatory framework with respect to EoW legislation in the entire EU, taking advantage of the experiences already grown in time in the MSs.

It is also worth mentioning that similar arguments are also included in the JRC technical proposal for EoW criteria for biodegradable waste treated as compost or digestate. The document highlights the lack of harmonization in the EU about a univocal way to determine whether a compost or digestate material is a waste or a product. In this framework, each MS has different ways to approach the matter e.g.: specific legislation for compost and digestates, direct approval of certain composts or digestates produced from waste-input materials as non-waste, obligation to consider all the composts and digestates as waste, possibility of case-by-case rules. The lack of harmonisation creates legal uncertainty for waste management decisions and for the different actors dealing with the material, including the producers and users of compost/digestate and investors. The uncertainty arises especially when trade between MSs is involved. Moreover, it limits the exchange of compost and digests across national borders, as a risk of administrative or penalties cost exists in the fragmented panorama, hampering the optimal development and up-scaling for the sector and slowing down the production.

Finally, from the interviews it emerged that another issue deserving attention is the case of multi-material packaging. For this flow, the recycle phase is more complex as it includes also the separation of single multi-material components. In this situation, the EoW criteria may be introduced for the waste as such, composed of different materials (the case of AHPs is an example of multi-material waste product) or after the components of the multi-material flow are separated, especially in the case they should be treated within different plants. The former case could be represented for example by packaging for milk or other beverages, for which is technically possible to separate and consequently recycle the paper fraction and the aluminium / PE fractions. The introduction of EoW for the aluminium / PE fractions, leaving the paper recycling plants would facilitate their treatment in other plants, avoiding their incineration.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Considering all these criticalities associated with the uptake of EoW criteria, combined with their high potential in supporting circular economy, they are also analysed not only in general terms, but also within the boundaries of the CIRCPACK value chains.

To this purpose, the conversion step from waste to secondary raw material for each demo case is analysed. Then, criticalities and potential application of EoW criteria of the material flows are investigated, thanks to the collaboration and availability of the industrial partners within the Project.

DC – A: Conversion of biomaterial scraps from film blowing extrusion process into biomaterial re-granulates, to be used for film blown extrusion and welding process (one cycle)

Biomaterial scraps and re-granulates from film blowing extrusion process are commonly internal scraps or by-product and consist of defective products detected and rejected by a quality control process during the manufacturing (such as thickness, appearance, colour) and production offcuts. This material is absorbed by the recycling process as a raw material and it is not registered as waste.

If biomaterial scrap leaves the specific facility where it was generated by blown film extrusion (for mechanical recycling or selling) it is a post-industrial waste and EoW criteria could be introduced here.

At current status, this application is at small scale experimental level and as such it is not yet clear the potential role of EoW criteria, which may turn useful but not necessarily crucial. Interest is to be expected from the material processing industries, from primary material to product.

Technical specifications for biomaterial scraps or re-granulates. The quality parameters to be put on the market may be introduced, also based on agreements between seller and buyer.

Currently, there are no EU standards dedicated to the recycling of biopolymers.

DC-B: Conversion of multi-material packaging into fibres to be reused in paper making and plastic components for the production of bioplastics

The conversion of multi-material packaging (i.e.: packaging composed by a cardboard layer coupled with a biobased dispersion coating) gives origin to a multi-material waste flow at first and consequently, after the separation of each material, through dispersion of the biobased coating in process waste, to two different waste flows: paper waste and side streams, composed with biobased coating dispersed in process water within CIRCPACK context.

Paper waste is commonly not seen as a waste, and it is referred to as paper for recycling, needed to produce secondary raw material. This favourable situation is possible thanks to the introduction of specifications about EoW criteria for paper waste in international

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

standards⁶⁷ widely applied in industry. These European standards are crucial to ensure circular schemes for paper waste on large scale. Technological processes and standards to reuse paper waste fibres for paper making are also consolidated.

According to the definition of paper and board for recycling reported by CEPI⁸, the multi-material packaging developed in CIRCPACK could reasonably belong to the flow of paper and board for recycling, and it can be discarded via paper bin. This fact would allow the up-scaling the recycling of both the paper and plastic components of the multi-material packaging.

The valorisation of side streams plastic components as secondary raw material is an innovative field. In detail, these side streams are generated at three different stages during the recycling process:

- at the screening stage, containing non-repulpable components, as reject;
- at the flotation stage, containing disintegrated non-dissolved small particles, such as inks and fillers, as sludges;
- at the water purification stage, as process water containing dissolved materials (colloidal materials and molecular substances such as sugars, proteins and salts).

The plastic components that end up in the process water during recycling can be subtracted from the process water through water purification. In case the waste definition applies to the side streams of the recycling process, depending also on potential transfers from one plant to another, valorisation of the plastic components (in the form of colloidal material) should be allowed and facilitated by an EoW criteria, allowing the use of plastic components from process water for the manufacturing of secondary raw bio-plastic.

The adoption of such criteria for the valorisation of process waste is recommended at EU level in order to minimize barriers for the trade of paper for recycling not only between EU countries, but also at global level, considering the significant size of the global market⁹. In addition, this would maximize also recycling rates, as because of the trade, it is hard to tell on forehand where the packaging will be recycled and thus maximum coverage is desirable. Currently, all the trade in paper for recycling in the EU has been regulated by the EN643¹⁰ and thus the coverage of EoW criteria acting on a material flow generated during paper recycling should be coherent and consistent with this status.

⁶ EN 643; European List of Standard Grades of Recovered Paper and Board

⁷ European Declaration on Paper Recycling

⁸ http://www.cepi.org/system/files/public/documents/publications/recycling/2013/CEPI_EN%20643_brochure_FINAL.pdf

⁹

http://www.cepi.org/system/files/public/documents/publications/statistics/2018/210X140_CEPI_Brochure_KeyStatistics2017_WEB.pdf

¹⁰ http://www.cepi.org/system/files/public/documents/publications/recycling/2013/CEPI_EN%20643_brochure_FINAL.pdf

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

The EoW criteria would allow the transport from the country where the packaging is discarded of to the country where the packaging will be recycled. As a consequence, the multi-material packaging developed in CIRCPACK could be produced and marketed in one country and end up in a recycling process at the other end of the EU or globe.

Moreover, when analysing the correspondent fossil-based value chain, in which carboard is coupled with a plastic layer, additional considerations emerge.

If the traditional multi-material packaging (paper with fossil-based plastic) is discarded of through the paper bin (not always allowed), it is regarded as Paper for Recycling and there may not be any troubles in processing it into paper, as secondary raw material. However, depending on the specific case, it may end-up to be considered as a rejected stream, not processable into secondary raw material and potentially used for incineration. Similarly, if the traditional multi-layer packaging is discarded of through any of the other waste bins, it is sorted out as waste and not recycled, but incinerated instead.

A reliable way to realize recycling of traditional multilayer packaging would be through the light-weight packaging bin separated collection. In some countries it is already allowed, and it enables a recycling process that is dedicated specifically to the recycle of multilayer packaging.

In case of such collection scheme, a set of EoW criteria for the respective multi-material packaging flow to be used for the production of separated materials (e.g.: fibres and plastic components) would likely facilitate transport, waste management and increase the options of use, possibly leading also to a decrease of waste management and secondary raw material costs.

DC-C: Conversion of polypropylene based plastic scraps into recycled polypropylene based scraps for non-automotive and automotive applications

For this application, the matter of proper management of industrial scrap is delicate and often associated with administrative burdens. Two different situations can arise:

- when the scrap material is not meant to leave the plant where it is generated, it is not treated as a waste. Nevertheless, it has to be properly labelled and codified to minimize the risk of confusion and mixing with other materials. In this situation, the complications arising are merely internal to the company and the specific plant;
- when the scrap material is meant to leave the plant where it is generated, additional complications related to the fact that it becomes an output of one plant and an input in another may arise, despite the fact that the two plants can belong to the same company/legal entity.

Currently, a viable approach for the management of scrap waste is to sell it to an external company as plastic raw material for non-automotive applications. This solution avoids that the scrap producer has to pay a waste management company to treat and dispose it.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

DC-C: Conversion of post-consumer and post-industrial plastic mixed waste (LDPE, LLDPE) into rLDPE and rLLDPE for film blown extrusion and bag sealing/welding

As each of the films has been performed with different materials and their origin is unknown, it is not possible to know all the different additives that might be present in each scenario. Although the results are good, the mechanical properties are not comparable between each other since both originated from different environments.

The introduction of EoW criteria is considered as crucial for the up-scaling of this step of DC-C.

For the requirements of input materials for post-consumer and post-industrial plastic mixed waste (LDPE, LLDPE) it should be taken into account that the options for recycling of waste plastic depend on the quality of the input materials.

Clean, contaminant free source of waste plastic (post-industrial) has more end-use options, higher market value and easier processing than a mixed and contaminated source of waste plastic (post-consumer). Inputs of waste shall be restricted to non-hazardous waste LDPE/LLDPE films used for packaging, construction and mulching, Acceptance control of all waste should be conducted by visual inspection and inspection of the accompanying documentation from supplier. The supplier should characterise plastic waste with a required data which are in technical specification or EU standard EN 15347: Plastics. Recycled Plastics. Characterisation of plastics wastes.

As far as the requirements of the treatment processes and techniques are concerned, waste plastic used as input shall be kept permanently separated from any other waste plastics.

Finally, in order to guarantee sufficient quality for recycled rLDPE and rLLDPE, a solution could be the monitoring of physical-chemical composition (as the pilot examples developed within CIRCPACK), content of impurities, physical size and shape in the recycling facility. In addition, specific technical specifications could be adopted in the case of buying and selling of rLDPE and rLLDPE. The quality parameters in specification could be agreed between seller and buyer or due to the relevant European standard for waste-plastic-based intermediates (e.g. regranulates) EN 15344: Plastics, Recycled plastics, Characterization of polyethylene (PE).

Such provisions could improve the quality of input materials for recycling (purchased post-industrial and post-consumer waste), leading to better quality of regranulates and less PE waste for landfilling.

DC-C: Conversion of AHPs waste into high-value cellulosic and plastics fractions to be used as secondary raw materials for an innovative plastic box and for mini-pallets

AHPs waste is mainly not recycled and belongs to “non-recyclable” municipal waste collection. It is typically disposed of via either landfill or incineration. Its profitable and environmentally advantageous conversion into secondary raw material has been

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

recently made possible in Italy thanks to the adoption of the EoW criteria for AHPs waste. The criteria have been strongly sought by FATER in the past years, in which the company, having the technological skills to treat this kind of waste, has dedicated high effort in overcoming legislative obstacles at regional and national level.

At current status, it would be desirable to extend the adoption of these criteria to other MSs and especially at EU level, in order to ensure a reliability for the operators of this sector and to encourage companies to start the same circular process.

Specific details on the EoW promoted in Italy for AHPs can be retrieved in English within the TRIS database¹¹ or in Italian in the national legislation portal¹².

In a similar field, additional flows for which the adoption of EoW criteria may be discussed are medical wastes, with particular reference to protective equipment such as masks. The adoption of the criteria as soon as the technology will allow sufficient quality for the recovered product for the same purpose or, alternatively, options for different end uses, the adoption of the criteria would speed-up the upscaling of this value chain and would encourage more companies to set-up similar businesses.

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/tris/en/index.cfm/search/?trisaction=search.detail&year=2019&num=36&mLang=IT>

¹² <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2019/07/08/19G00071/sg>

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

6 STAKEHOLDERS CONSULTATION

In order to identify the most important barriers and to select the most effective policy recommendations, a stakeholders consultation has been performed. The consultation is intended to investigate existing perceptions of educated participants with regard to the issue of circularity within the value chain of plastic packaging material, analysing both barriers and policy measures to overcome such barriers. The respondents provide a significant coverage of the EU, including Italy, Croatia, Spain, Turkey, Norway, Germany and also a significant coverage of the fields related to the plastic packaging value chain, including compliance scheme, waste management companies and reprocessors, plastic and bio plastic material manufacturers, local government, NGOs and business representative organisation, universities and research centres, consulting companies and individuals.

The entire text of the consultation is included as Annex B.

In the first part of the consultation, participants are asked to give a qualitative score (very important / important / slightly important / unimportant) to the relevance of a list of barriers retrieved from an extensive and updated literature analysis. The barriers presented are categorized into: general barriers, economic barriers, barriers concerning awareness and engagement issues, barriers concerning technological and design issues, barriers concerning traceability and standardization and finally barriers specific for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastic streams.

In the second part of the consultation, a number of measures is identified. Each measure is associated to a rationale, describing the main purpose of the measure and recalling the relevant barriers previously introduced. In addition, each rationale is enriched by one or more examples of best practices, useful to guide the selection of effective measures to address the barriers. Participants are questioned about the desirability and the potential recipient legislative framework for each measure.

The main outcomes of the consultation are presented in the sections below.

6.1 OUTCOMES: BARRIERS

Table 8 summarizes the results of the survey for the analysed barriers. Overall, it is worth noting that barriers with an overall importance higher or equal to 90% belong to variegated categories, namely economic (2/4 barriers), technological and design (2/4 barriers), general legislative (2/6 barriers), supply chain (1/3 barriers), awareness and engagement (1/2 barriers). None of the barriers belonging to the traceability and standardization category and addressing biobased, biodegradable and compostable specific issue exceeds 90% of importance. However, it shall be highlighted that all the barriers were highlighted as important or very important by the majority of the respondents.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Table 8. Overall results – Barriers (VI: very important, I: important, U: unimportant)

Barrier	VI, I	U
Lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice	95%	5%
Many recycling processes are still not optimal, leading to a loss in material quality and quantity	95%	0%
Use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer	90%	5%
Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers	90%	0%
Possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation	90%	0%
The cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues	90%	0%
The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling	90%	0%
Lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of plastic waste management	90%	0%
Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging	86%	5%
Low capillarity of re-processing plants and logistic issues	86%	0%
Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material	86%	5%
Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design	86%	10%
Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics and by the lack of efficient separate collection of bio-waste in all MSs.	86%	5%
Absence of End of Waste criteria for plastic packaging waste	86%	5%
Lack of citizens education about correct waste management	81%	0%
A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products	81%	0%
Lack of composting facilities able to treat all types of bio-waste (as defined by WFD) and to produce high quality content	81%	10%

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Barrier	VI, I	U
Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion	81%	0%
Material incineration – as a form of down-cycling of plastic packaging - can be cheaper than recycling	81%	10%
Lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging	76%	0%
Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging	71%	5%
Landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries	67%	5%
The meaning of “bioplastic” covers a variety of different materials, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both	62%	14%
Difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials	57%	5%
Nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process	57%	0%

Finally, it is pointed out that the following barriers were evaluated as very important by a share of respondents higher than 50%:

- lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of plastic waste management;
- lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice;
- inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers;
- lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to account for environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging;
- lack of citizens education about correct waste management;
- a sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products.

If analysing the specific answers of the internal Stakeholders participating to the Survey, the barriers that they all consider very important are:

- inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers.

The results obtained for the barriers are aligned with the outcomes generated by the business workshops in D7.9 “Social acceptance report and results of testing with real

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

consumers: approaches for different stakeholders". For the specific case of the Italian stakeholders meeting, moderated by RINA-C and hosted by FATER S.p.A., the main findings highlighted the lack of awareness across the actors and among citizens and end-users, lack of legislative barriers and the lack of economic incentives as main obstacles to overcome. Moreover, also during the 1st stakeholders meeting of the CIRCPACK project, held in Brussels (April 2018), RINA presented the progress about legislative barriers and also chaired one of the stakeholders roundtables. The main outcomes of the workshop in terms of barriers from the business side, the most relevant for this Task, highlighted the importance of barriers concerning bureaucracy as well as the security of the supply chain.

6.1.1 General legislative barriers

Figure 6.1 shows the importance of the general legislative barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 50% for all the barriers).

Specifically, *"possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation"* and *"use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer"* are the barriers with highest importance while, *"difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials"* is the barrier with the lowest importance. Finally, none of the respondents assessed the barrier *"possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation"* as unimportant.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Figure 6.1. Importance of general legislative barriers

6.1.2 Supply chain barriers

Figure 6.2 shows the importance of the supply chain barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 70% for all the barriers).

Specifically, “inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers” is the barrier with highest importance while, “existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging” is the barrier with the lowest importance. Finally, none of the respondents assessed the two aforementioned barriers as unimportant.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Figure 6.2. Importance of supply chain barriers

6.1.3 Economic barriers

Figure 6.3 shows the importance of the economic barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 70% for all the barriers).

Specifically, “*lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice*” is the barrier with highest importance while, “*lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging*” is the barrier with the lowest importance. Finally, none of the respondents assessed “*lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging*” and “*the cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues*” unimportant, and about 10% of the respondents assessed “*material incineration – as a form of down-cycling of plastic packaging – can be cheaper than recycling*”.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Figure 6.3. Importance of economic barriers

6.1.4 Awareness and engagement barriers

Figure 6.4 shows the importance of the awareness and engagement barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 80% for all the barriers). In addition, none of the respondents assessed these barriers as unimportant.

Figure 6.4. Importance of awareness and engagement barriers

6.1.5 Technological and design barriers

Figure 6.5 shows the importance of the technological and design barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 50% for all the barriers).

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Specifically, “many recycling processes are still not optimal, leading to a loss in material quality and quantity” is the barrier with highest importance while, “nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process” is the barrier with the lowest importance. Finally, none of the respondents assessed these barriers as unimportant.

Figure 6.5. Importance of technological and design barriers

6.1.6 Traceability and standardization barriers

Figure 6.6 shows the importance of the traceability and standardization barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 80% for all the barriers).

Overall, the level of importance is homogeneous among these barriers, however about 10% of the respondents assessed “low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design” as unimportant.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Figure 6.6. Importance of traceability and standardization barriers

6.1.7 Biobased, biodegradable and compostable products specific barriers

Figure 6.7 shows the importance of the biobased, biodegradable and compostable products specific barriers according to the results of the survey. Overall, all the barriers are considered by the majority of the respondents as very important or important (with a total share over 60% for all the barriers).

Specifically, “difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics and by the lack of efficient separate collection of bio-waste in all MSs” is the barrier with highest importance while, “the meaning of “bioplastic” covers a variety of different materials, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both” is the barrier with the lowest importance. Finally, about 10% of the respondents and about 15% of the respondents assessed “lack of composting facilities able to treat all types of bio-waste (as defined by WFD) and to produce high quality content” and “the meaning of “bioplastic” covers a variety of different materials, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both” respectively as unimportant.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Figure 6.7. Importance of biobased, biodegradable and compostable products specific barriers

6.2 OUTCOMES: MEASURES

This section illustrates the outcomes of the survey in terms of measure identified to address existing barriers towards circular economy in plastic packaging.

Table 9 shows the proposed measures in order of importance. In addition, for each measure, together with information about the most suitable recipient legislative framework(s) (i.e.: EU, national, local/regional), as assessed by the respondents.

Above all, the measures for which importance was agreed by all the respondents are:

- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling);
- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content;
- incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria;
- reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions;
- encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies.

More in detail, a clear demand for the promotion and up-scaling of eco-designed, products exists. The participants explicitly expressed the desire to introduce EPR schemes specific for biodegradable and compostable packaging, to ensure that also composter receive fees for waste reprocessing.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Also measures addressing the introduction of waste management tariff schemes based on the actual amount of waste produced, increase of consumers' awareness towards improved waste management, promotion of research about effective waste management systems, definition of EoW criteria for fossil-based and bio-based plastic streams.

As far as suitable legislative frameworks are concerned, the majority of respondents states that for almost the majority of the measures (except 3), shall be adopted at least at EU level, which is also seen as particularly adapt for the development of research initiatives in the fields of recycling technologies and ,biobased, biodegradable and compostable materials, the definition of EoW criteria as well as the creation of an homogeneous background for eco-design requirements for packaging products and official vocabulary. At National level, measures such as incentive responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices in private companies and development of research initiatives in the fields of recycling technologies and biobased, biodegradable and compostable materials should be primarily promoted. The regional/local framework – in combination with other legislations – is seen as suitable to implement measures for an improvement of urban waste management, in terms of awareness raising and implementation of tariff schemes for waste collection.

Overall, it appears that the measures ensuring a significant and constant demand for sustainable products, from large companies or public authorities are firmly desired, mostly at EU and national level. In addition, the measures addressing the establishment of a more effective waste management systems, especially on behalf of the consumers are encouraged, mostly at EU level and at national level as far as awareness raising initiatives are concerned.

If focusing on the opinions of the internal partners, the measures agreed as very desirable are:

- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling) – to be adopted at national and/or EU level
- Promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials – to be adopted at least at EU level;
- Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics – to be adopted at least at EU level.

The results obtained for the measures are quite aligned with the outcomes generated by the business workshops in D7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders", which are however more oriented towards a general increase of awareness, a harmonization of EU legislation and an improvement of eco-design and waste management technical and technological solutions. For the specific case of the Italian stakeholders meeting, moderated by RINA-C and hosted by FATER S.p.A., the main findings highlighted the need of increasing

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

awareness as well as of promoting labels and standards of environmental performance and introducing fiscal incentives. Moreover, also during the 1st stakeholders meeting of the CIRCPACK project, held in Brussels (April 2018), RINA presented the progress about legislative barriers and also chaired one of the stakeholders roundtables. The main outcomes of the workshop in terms of measures barriers from the business side, the most relevant for this Task, highlighted the importance of introducing EoW criteria coupled with incentives or tax reduction, in order to make the circular chain economically sustainable.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Table 9. Overall results – Measures (VI: very important, I: important, U: unimportant)

Measure	VI, I	U	EU	National	Regional / local
Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling)	100%	0%	62%	57%	33%
Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content	100%	0%	57%	48%	33%
Incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria	100%	0%	48%	71%	19%
Reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions	100%	0%	48%	57%	24%
Encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies	100%	0%	81%	67%	14%
Launch the establishment of waste management tariff schemes based on the amount of waste actually produced and on the quality of sorting achieved	95%	0%	52%	48%	43%
Increase consumers' awareness about the importance of implementing virtuous waste management practices and increase guidance on sorting procedures available in their area, in order to increase the level of separation and to increase the overall quality and efficiency of the recycling process	95%	0%	38%	57%	48%
Promote research to structure the most effective waste management system (e.g.: collection, sorting at plant, sorting at consumers) in relation with citizens' awareness level, urban geographical context, available technologies, etc.	95%	0%	71%	67%	24%
Define EoW for fossil plastic waste streams	95%	5%	76%	24%	0%
Define EoW for bio-plastic waste streams	95%	0%	76%	43%	5%
Guarantee use of a homogeneous terminology with respect to waste and waste management across different policies and different sectors	90%	0%	76%	52%	5%
Facilitate negotiating mechanisms for trade agreements that allow to increase recovery rates, to reduce recovery tariffs and to accelerate materials import and export	90%	0%	52%	38%	5%

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Measure	VI, I	U	EU	National	Regional / local
Increase consumers' awareness about packaging design, properties and values through standardized labels, including on products precise statements about the presence of multi-material packaging, separable packaging parts, biobased material	90%	0%	67%	43%	19%
Introduce more stringent Essential Requirements for packaging products to be put on the market and establish control schemes to ensure compliance of products with such requirements	90%	0%	81%	29%	0%
Increase transparency in waste traceability, by encouraging municipalities or entities responsible for waste management to create robust datasets for each waste streams and by introducing certificates of waste treatments performed and source of waste material	90%	0%	62%	52%	38%
Promote environmental labels and product declaration for packaging product, covering the entire life cycle	90%	0%	67%	48%	10%
Boost networking initiatives for industrial stakeholders committed to the achievement of a circular and sustainable economy for plastic packaging and their connection with other industrial sectors	86%	0%	57%	48%	24%
Promote design best practices and guidelines across the plastic packaging manufacturing industry	86%	0%	62%	43%	14%
Introduce minimum requirements for secondary raw material specifications and labels	86%	0%	62%	38%	5%
Promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials	86%	0%	76%	38%	14%
Introduce incentives to guarantee that the most sustainable recycling routes are cost-effective compared with the other available options (e.g.: incineration)	81%	0%	57%	33%	24%
Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics	81%	0%	62%	33%	24%
Promote eco-designed packaging solutions and waste prevention in packaging design within the EPR schemes, for example by introducing quantitative targets on such performances	76%	0%	57%	52%	10%
Introduce landfill bans or increase landfill costs in order to make recycle more cost effective and – in parallel – introduce incentives or tax exemptions to decrease the cost of recycle of certain plastic streams	76%	10%	52%	38%	5%
Encourage collaboration between Member States, in order to align their approach and narrow the existing gaps as much as possible	71%	0%	62%	33%	5%
Ban certain traditional fossil-based plastic products and – in parallel – facilitate the commercialization of innovative equivalent bio-based compostable products	62%	5%	62%	24%	14%

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

7 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the analyses performed in the previous paragraphs, a set of policy recommendations is extracted, based on the results of the stakeholders' consultation and on the opinions collected from the Project partners. The list of recommendations is presented below:

- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling)** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria** – to be adopted at least at national level;
- **reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions** – to be adopted at least at national level, but possibly also at EU level;
- **encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials** – to be adopted at least at EU level, but possibly also at national level;
- **introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics** – to be adopted at least at EU level.

Moreover, **a harmonized adoption of EoW for plastic-waste streams criteria should be promoted at EU level**, while the same measure seems less crucial for the case of biodegradable and compostable plastic waste. Among the value chains experimented within the CIRCPACK project, it results that the use of EoW criteria would be particularly desired for the conversion side-streams of paper recycling process in the case of multi-material packaging, of post-consumer and post-industrial plastic mixed waste (LDPE, LLDPE) into rLDPE and rLLDPE for film blown extrusion and bag sealing/welding and for conversion of AHPs waste into high-value cellulosic and plastics fractions to be used as secondary raw materials for an innovative plastic box and for mini-pallets.

Input to EC Stakeholders' Consultation

In October 2018, in cooperation with the partners of the Consortium, within T6.3 activities, RINA-C guided the compilation of the **European Stakeholders' consultation "Future climate and energy policy - a Strategy for long-term EU greenhouse gas emissions**

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

reductions¹³. The consultation aimed at collecting views and opinions on the technological and socio-economic pathways that should be explored for a long-term EU GHG emissions reduction strategy and at gathering factual information, data and knowledge about elements not covered by reporting exercises, including drivers and barriers, challenges and opportunities relevant to the long-term strategy.

Only the questions relevant for the purposes of the CIRCPACK project were filled. The submitted version is included as Annex C.

Among other inputs, the results of the consultation contributed to the development of the 2050 long-term strategy, embedded within the EU Green Deal.

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/consultations/strategy-long-term-eu-greenhouse-gas-emissions-reductions_en

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

8 CONCLUSIONS

This Deliverable, considered as the prosecution of the work presented in D6.4, has the overall aim to identify **a set of policy recommendations for EU institutions to promote and facilitate circular economy-based schemes for plastic packaging streams, with a focus on the recycling phase.**

As complementary contents, an update of the **legislative framework at EU and national level** for Italy, Spain, Croatia and Turkey is presented. From the analysis of the policies presented, there are not major changes strictly related to the plastic recycling sector, at all levels. However, at EU level, the Single Use Plastics Directive and the European Green Deal surely represent major interventions towards circular economy in the plastic sector. As relevant remarks, the adoption of the EoW criteria for AHPs in Italy and the modifications of the waste management systems in Croatia are mentioned. Moreover, **factsheets about main legislative framework and waste management systems** are presented for a wider set of Member States, among those involved in the adoption of the first Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive.

A focused analysis on **EoW criteria** has shed light on the most crucial aspects about EoW legislation in the EU, highlighting mostly the need of harmonization of legislative framework among the MSs and suggesting some potential application for the CIRCPACK value chains.

Finally, as a result of a **stakeholders' consultation** performed within CIRCPACK, major barriers and measures for circular economy in the plastic packaging sector are analysed. **Barriers** with an overall importance higher or equal to 90% according to the participants belong to variegated categories, namely economic, technological and design, general legislative, supply chain, awareness and engagement. Furthermore, it appears that the **measures** ensuring a significant and constant demand for sustainable products, from large companies or public authorities are firmly desired, mostly at EU and national level. In addition, the measures addressing the establishment of a more effective waste management systems, especially on behalf of the consumers are encouraged, mostly at EU level and at national level as far as awareness raising initiatives are concerned.

As final output of the work, the following set of **policy recommendations** addressed at EU institutions is presented:

- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling);
- introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content;
- incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria;
- reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions;

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

- encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies;
- promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials; introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

9 REFERENCES

BIO Intelligence Service, 2011. Awareness and Exchange of Best Practices on the Implementation and Enforcement of the Essential Requirements for Packaging and Packaging Waste, Draft Final Report prepared for European Commission, DG ENV.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 3.4 "Report on sorting and recyclability of new Biomaterials and Biopackaging, adaptation of current recycling protocols", prepared by MI-PLAST, AITIIP, NOVAMONT, CALAF. 2020.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 5.1 "Report on recycling methodology for packaging sector, possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology", prepared by MI-PLAST. 2019.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 5.2 "Report on recycling methodology for automotive sector and possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology", prepared by CRF. 2019.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 5.3 "Report on recycling methodology for absorbent hygienic products, possible adaptation and upgrade of the technology", prepared by FATER. 2019.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 6.4 "Legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil and biobased plastics for packaging", prepared by RINA. 2018.

CIRCPACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain (GA n° 730423). Deliverable 7.9 "Social acceptance report and results of testing with real consumers: approaches for different stakeholders", prepared by OKU. 2020.

Crippa, M., De Wilde, B., Koopmans, R., Leyssens, J., Muncke, J., Ritschkoff A-C., Van Doorselaer, K., Velis, C. & Wagner, M. A circular economy for plastics – Insights from research and innovation to inform policy and funding decisions, 2019 (M. De Smet & M. Linder, Eds.). European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.

European Bioplastics. <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/about-us/>

European Bioplastics, 2017. Bioplastics – Industry standards & labels: Factsheet.

European Circular economy Stakeholder Platform. <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en>

European Commission, 2016. The efficient functioning of waste markets in the European Union legislative and policy options – Legislative and policy options. Final report.

European Commission, 2017. Public Procurement for a Circular Economy – Good Practice Guidance.

European Commission, 2018. A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

European economic and social Committee and the Committee of the regions. Brussels, 16.1.2018 COM(2018) 28 final.

European Commission, 2018. A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment – Updated Bioeconomy Strategy.

European Commission, 2018. EU Plastics Strategy: Commission welcomes voluntary pledges from industry to boost the market for recycled plastics and encourages further action – Press Release.

European Commission, 2019. Sustainable Products in a Circular Economy - Towards an EU Product Policy Framework contributing to the Circular Economy. Commission staff working document. Brussels, 4.3.2019 SWD(2019) 91 final.

European Commission, 2019. Report on the implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan. Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European economic and social Committee and the Committee of the regions. Brussels, 4.3.2019 COM(2019) 190 final.

European Commission, 2019. The European Green Deal. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European economic and social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Brussels, 11.12.2019 COM(2019) 640 final.

European Commission, 2020. Proposal for a Regulation of The European Parliament and of the Council establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (European Climate Law). Brussels, 4.3.2020 COM(2020) 80 final.

European Commission, 2020. A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Brussels, 11.3.2020 COM(2020) 98 final.

European Commission, 2020. Circular Economy Action Plan for a cleaner and more competitive Europe.

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2019. A circular economy for plastics - Insights from research and innovation to inform policy and funding decisions. EU publications.

European Committee of the Regions, Commission for the Environment, Climate Change and Energy, 2018. A European Strategy for plastics in the circular economy - Local and regional dimension.

European Environmental Agency. Country factsheets on resource efficiency and circular economy in Europe. 2019.

European Sustainable Business Federation, 2019. Circular Economy Update – Overview of Circular Economy in Europe.

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

European Parliament and European Council, 2019. DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/904 of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment.

European Union Network for the Implementation of Environmental Law, 2019. Making the Circular Economy Work - Guidance for regulators on enabling innovations for the circular economy (prevention and recycling of waste).

Fortum Corporation, 2019. Fortum Plastics Review.

ICF, eunomia, 2018. Plastics: Reuse, recycling and marine litter. European Commission.

Joint Research Centre, 2014. End-of-waste criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate): Technical proposals.

Joint Research Centre, 2014. End-of-waste criteria for waste plastic for conversion: Technical proposals.

Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy. https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/node/2_it

N. Johansson, C. Forsgren, Is this the end of end-of-waste? Uncovering the space between waste and products, Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Volume 155, 2020, 104656, ISSN 0921-3449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104656>.

OECD, 2018. Improving Plastics Management: Trends, policy responses, and the role of international co-operation and trade, OECD Environment Policy Papers, No. 12, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/c5f7c448-en>.

Plasteurope. <https://www.plasteurope.com/default.asp>

R. Pardo, J.P Schweitzer, 2018. 'A long-term strategy for a European circular economy – setting the course for success', Policy Paper produced for the Think2030 project, Brussels, November 2018.

Republic of Turkey, Zero Waste Regulation, Official Gazette, 12 July 2019/30829.

Republic of Turkey, Waste Control Regulation, Official Gazette, 2 April 2015/29314, revision 23 March 2017/30016.

Republic of Turkey, Amending Law on the Environmental Law and Some Laws, Official Gazette, 10 December 2018/30621.

Republic of Turkey, Procedures and Principles Regarding Pricing of Plastic Bags, 25 December 2018, revision 9 January 2019 and 31 December 2019, Ministry of Environment and Urbanization.

Republic of Turkey, Turkish Food Codex Communiqué on Food Contact Plastic Materials and Articles, Official Gazette, 25 December 2019/30989.

Republic of Turkey, Regulation on Control of Packaging Waste, Official Gazette 27 December 2017/30283, revised In March 2020.

The Italian Institute of Packaging, 2018. VADEMECUM for packaging management.

TRIS Database under Directive (EU) 2015/1535. <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/tris/en/>

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Turkish Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, Zero Waste System.
<http://zerowaste.gov.tr/en/zero-waste/types-of-waste/plastic-waste>

World Economic Forum and Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017. The New Plastics Economy – Catalysing action

World Economic Forum, Ellen MacArthur Foundation and McKinsey & Company, 2016. The New Plastics Economy — Rethinking the future of plastics.

WRAP, 2013. Working with compostable products and packaging in closed venue events.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

ANNEX A – POLICY FRAMEWORK IN SOME MEMBER STATES

Austria

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	The Austrian Resource Efficiency Action Plan was adopted in 2012. The Austrian Bioeconomy Strategy was published in 2019. It acts as a framework for the reinforced use of renewable raw materials and it aims at identifying concrete measures for the further establishment of bioeconomy within the Country. The implementation of the strategy will be monitored via an Action Plan, currently under development.
Specific Measures	The main specific policy measures address the reduction of plastic shopping bags, in a significantly more stringent way than the one adopted at EU level. The Austrian voluntary agreement on shopping bags, published in 2016, aims to reduce the use of plastic shopping bags by 50 per cent by 2019, a target of about 25 plastic bags per person per year by 2019. In addition, the Cabinet approved a ban on non-biodegradable plastic bags set to come into effect in Austria at the start of 2020.

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	EPR systems	EPR systems Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	EPR systems Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Austrian market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Importers SHALL subscribe to one (or more) of the following producer responsibility organizations accredited, with payment of related fee (public but different for each system):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARA AG • INTERSEROH • LANDBELL • RECLAY ÖSTERREICH • OKO BOX (for beverage cartons, currently within ARA AG system) 	<p>Importers CAN subscribe to one (or more) of the following producer responsibility organizations accredited:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARA AG • INTERSEROH • LANDBELL • RECLAY ÖSTERREICH • OKO BOX (for beverage cartons, currently within ARA AG system). <p>Alternatively, the services can be developed by the producer itself (self-compliance) or through the different operators available on the market.</p>

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARA
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to ARA members and related suppliers (through copy of the license)

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Key Issues

Highlights
Producers of goods can possibly replace importers on the basis of a written agreement signed by the parties, negotiated within the commercial contract of supply/purchase.
In Austria the definition of urban/domestic packaging waste is based on 2 criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none">Dimension of packaging: max surface area = 1.5 m², max nominal volume = 5 l, or max mass = 0.15 kg, included for unit sold for EPS made packaging (e.g. polystyrene);Type of waste producer: families or business such as restaurants, bars, hotels, cafeterias, tobacco shops, public and private offices, barracks, hospitals and medical clinics, schools, charity organizations, cinemas and theatres, opera and museums, touristic and sport structures, parcs, wellness centres, service areas and other micro-enterprises.
In Austria the definition of packaging is more specifically detailed also depending on product category of the packaged good.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Belgium

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>Main publications addressing circular economy in Belgian policies include the Strategy for the Circular Economy (2014) and the 21 measures of the federal government for a circular economy "Let's make the economy work by developing the circular economy in Belgium" (2016). However, it shall be highlighted that in Belgium there is no national resource efficiency or circular economy strategy/action plan in force, as the matter of material resource efficiency and circular economy are considered as transversal, involving several policy levels. Responsibilities and competences are assigned at various scales, from regional to national.</p> <p>All the regions have landfill and incineration bans and pay as you throw schemes for households waste</p> <p>In Flanders region, the public regional waste agency (OVAM) set up in 2018 a national platform for the circular economy, through which the top levels of federal and regional environment departments, economy/innovation departments and finance departments meet twice a year to decide on common action in priority policy fields. As for the field of bioeconomy, the Flanders launched the Bioeconomy Strategy in 2014, covering the time-span until 2030.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>The federal government launched several initiatives to support the enhancement of circular economy for plastic and packaging. As an example, they aim at the integration of recycled plastic content into market evaluation criteria, plastic decontamination techniques to support healthy recycling. A ban on disposable plastic bags is in place since 2016. Moreover, an ex-ante evaluation of the introduction of deposit systems for single-use beverage packaging in Flanders can lead to an increase in the recycling rate of single-use packaging, especially of PET bottles. However, the deposit has not been introduced.</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities	EPR systems
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	EPR systems

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Belgian market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Importers and producers SHALL subscribe to the FOST PLUS no profit organization, by paying a fee to finance collection, sorting and waste treatment.</p>	<p>Importers and producers SHALL subscribe to the VALIPAC no profit organization, by paying a fee to finance collection, sorting and waste treatment.</p>

Labelling

Details	
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FOST PLUS
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to FOST PLUS members and related suppliers (through copy of the license)

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Key Issues

Highlights
In Belgium the definition of urban/domestic packaging waste is based on an indicative list drafted by FOST PLUS and VALIPAC

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Denmark

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	Denmark relies on resource strategy and plan for waste management "Denmark Without Waste, Recycle More – Incinerate Less" (2013) and a waste prevention strategy "Denmark Without Waste II, Strategy for Waste Prevention" (2015). In addition, the Danish Government adopted the Strategy for a Circular Economy "More value and better environment through design, consumption, and recycling" (2018), supporting the acceleration the circular development across 6 overarching objectives and 15 initiatives.
Specific Measures	The Danish government adopted an Action Plan on Plastics (2018). The Action Plan on Plastics, addressing, among others, an expansion of the deposit-return system to cover also bottles used for fruit juices and fruit concentrates, ban on lightweight plastic carrier bags and better sorting of plastic waste.

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities, deposit system for recycling	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	Local authorities, deposit system for recycling	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Danish market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Importers and producers of beverages packaging SHALL subscribe to the deposit system DANSK RETURN SYSTEM</p>	<p>Importers and producers SHALL rely on services offered by private companies</p>

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DANSK RETURN SYSTEM
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deposit mark: compulsory for one-way packaging. It consists of five black dots, as well as the letters "Pant A", "Pant B" or "Pant C", depending on the value of the deposit

Penalties

	Details
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper use of "Pant" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use. • Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Finland

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>The Strategic Programme (2015) sets a 10-year objective stating that Finland will be a pioneer in the bioeconomy, circular economy and cleantech. Concrete action includes increased recovery of nutrients, increased recycling rates of municipal waste to reach at least 50 per cent, and a ban on sending recyclable waste to landfill by 2025. In line with the Programme, Finland adopted its Roadmap to Circular Economy for 2016-2025, recently updated in 2019. The document highlights best practice and pilots that can be easily replicated and provide added value on a national scale.</p> <p>The Plastics Roadmap for Finland (2018) "identifies measures to reduce the harm caused by plastic waste and litter, help consumers take plastics to waste management, improve the efficiency of plastics recovery, recycling and product design, create conditions for investments and innovations in the circular economy, and make us less dependent on fossil raw materials by increasing bio-based and biodegradable solutions".</p> <p>Moreover, the Finnish Bioeconomy Strategy (2014) set the following goals:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. a competitive operating environment for the bioeconomy;2. new business from the bioeconomy;3. a strong bioeconomy competence base;4. accessibility and sustainability of biomass.
Specific Measures	<p>In addition, so-called Green Deals between Ministries and industry allow to enforce voluntary agreements to promote the circular economy and mitigate climate change. Among the Deals, one is dedicated to the reduction of plastic carrier bags consumption.</p> <p>As far as recycling and recovery of packaging are concerned, it is noticed that thanks to the EPR systems in place, in the Helsinki region, the collection of plastic packaging waste is cheaper than the collection of mixed municipal solid waste. Furthermore, Finland is successful in the collection and recycling of drinks packaging, also due to the drinks packaging tax, currently paid on packaging for water, alcoholic beverages, beer and soft drinks.</p>

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	EPR systems + deposit system for recycling or tax scheme	EPR systems
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems + deposit system for recycling or tax scheme	EPR systems

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Finnish market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 <p>Beverages packaging accredited to Ekopullo Association or PALPA can benefit from a reduction/exemption of the environmental tax based on the recovery route</p>	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Importers and producers of beverages packaging SHALL pay a fee on packaging, if they do not subscribe to a deposit for reuse or recycle or to an EPR system.</p> <p>Importers and producers of other packaging type SHALL subscribe to the no-profit compliance scheme PYR-RINKI, by paying a fee to finance collection, sorting and waste treatment.</p>	

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Labelling

Details	
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE, integrated with specific labels to sort packaging.
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DANSK RETURNSYSTEM
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">"Pant": compulsory for non-reusable beverage containers subject to deposit schemes

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

France

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>France adopted a Road Map for the Circular Economy (2018) that allows all the main actors to move towards this direction. It also aims to enable France. Among the main objectives of the Roadmap there is “to progress towards 100 per cent recycled plastics in 2025” and “to reduce greenhouse gas emissions: saving the emission of 8 million tonnes of additional carbon dioxide each year through the recycling of plastic”. The 50 measures of the Roadmap on the Circular Economy encompass action to promote the use of secondary raw materials and bio-materials.</p> <p>The Bioeconomy Strategy (2017) describes the challenges of the bio-economy. It is accompanied by the Bioeconomy Action Plan (2018), describing the concrete action to be taken.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>The French waste policy is characterised by a large number of EPR schemes, important for waste recycling and implementing the eco-modulation of feed.</p> <p>In addition, the Ministry of Environment plans to introduce penalties on non-recycled plastics.</p> <p>The French Government launched the National Pact of Plastic Packaging (2019), addressing specific issues for the plastic packaging, such as eco-design, reusability, recyclability, compostability, biodegradability, recycled content targets.</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the French market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Producers and importers SHALL subscribe to one (or more) producer responsibility organizations (PRO) accredited. As an example, CITEO is a no profit organization with a subscription fee depending on the amount and type of packaging to be managed</p>	<p>Producers of commercial and industrial packaging waste (exceeding 1,100 liters/week) SHALL independently manage wastes to reach the recycle target (self-compliance)</p>

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decree n° 2014-1577, introducing the mark "Triman". This mark communicates the recyclability of products covered by EPR schemes and separate collection.
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CITEO
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to ARA members and related suppliers (through copy of the license)

Penalties

	Details
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Key Issues

Highlights

There are cases in which also companies exporting packaged goods to France subscribe to the CITEO scheme

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Germany

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>Currently, there is not dedicated circular economy strategy or programme in Germany. However, this theme is embedded in different pieces of policy.</p> <p>The Federal government adopted the German Resource Efficiency Programme (2012, updated in 2016) and committed itself to reporting every four years on the development of resource efficiency in Germany, assessing progress and updating its programme. The Programme intends to make the extraction and use of natural resources more sustainable. It is built on four principles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• combining ecological necessities with economic opportunities, innovation focus, and social responsibility;• seeing global responsibility as a key guide of national resource policy;• making economic and production activities in Germany depend less and less on primary resources, and developing and expanding the circular economy;• securing sustainable resource use for the long term by guiding society towards quality growth. <p>In its waste policy (2012), the government is explicitly pursuing the goal of the development of waste and closed-cycle management into a sustainable and resource-efficient management of material flows.</p> <p>The National Policy Strategy on Bioeconomy (2013), defines priorities on the way towards a knowledge-based bioeconomy and plots the needed action. An updated National Policy Strategy on Bioeconomy (2020) has been recently adopted, laying down the guidelines and objectives for its policy on the bioeconomy and lists measures for their implementation.</p> <p>The Strategy is matched coherently with other legislations in force and it is built on the Research Strategy for Bioeconomy 2030 – Our Path towards a Bio-based Economy (2015). The overarching aim of the research strategy is to promote the sustainable use of biological resources through bio-innovation and its application in various industrial sectors to improve material efficiency, climate protection and the use of materials from renewable sources.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>A new Packaging Act (2019) has entered force with increased recycling targets, incentives for reuse and design for recycling, mandatory registration with the central packaging registry and fees based on environmental performance.</p>

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (Producers)	Companies (Producers)
Collection	EPR systems + deposit system for recycling	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems + deposit system for recycling	Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the German market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Producers and importers (excluding the case of beverages containers) SHALL subscribe to one (or more) producer responsibility organizations (PRO) accredited:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BELLANDIVISION • DER GRÜNE PUNKT – Duale System Deutschland • INTERSEROH • LANDBELL • RECLAY Vfw – REDUAL • RKD Recycling Kontor Dual • VEOLIA • ZENTEK • ELS Europäische Lizenzierungs Systeme <p>Producers and importers of beverage containers SHALL subscribe to the deposit system PFAND</p>	<p>Producers of commercial and industrial packaging waste can rely on EPR schemes or private operators</p>

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Labelling

Details	
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DER GRÜNE PUNKT• PFAND
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to DER GRÜNE PUNKT members and related suppliers (through copy of the license)• "DPG": for packaging managed by PFAND

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improper use of "Green Dot" is not associated with specific penalties, but DER GRÜNE PUNKT may sue companies making improper use of the mark

Key Issues

Highlights
Companies exporting packaged products to Germany may be required to comply to German legislation, if specific bilateral agreements are not stipulated between the exporting and importing companies

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Greece

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>Greece recently adopted the "National Action Plan on Circular Economy" (2018), centred around a long-term adoption and implementation of circular economy principles. Priority actions include removing barriers to a circular economy through new regulatory and legislative interventions, designating funds for these interventions, enhancing knowledge on circular economy and improving governance structures by establishing an Executive Secretariat for the Circular Economy.</p> <p>The long-term (2030) goals of the National Action Plan on Circular Economy foresee a focus on prevention and recycle, enhancement of industrial symbiosis, support to circular consumption patterns, encouragement of multi-stakeholder partnerships and monitoring progress towards a circular economic model.</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods and packaging products)
Collection	Local authorities, EPR systems	EPR systems, Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	EPR systems, Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Greek market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Producers and importers SHALL subscribe to one producer responsibility organizations (PRO) accredited:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HERCCO • Rewarding Recycling – Antapodotiki Anakiklosi <p>or to an autonomous accredited (self-compliance)</p>	<p>Producers of commercial and industrial packaging waste can subscribe to HERCCO or independently manage wastes (self-compliance)</p>

Labelling

Details	
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HERCCO
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Green Dot”: voluntary use, allowed to HERCCO members

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper use of “Green Dot” registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Ireland

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>The development of a specific Strategy on Circular Economy in Ireland is currently ongoing.</p> <p>However, the National Planning Framework Ireland 2040 (2018) includes explicit reference to the principles of the circular economy, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support the circular and bio economy including in particular through greater efficiency in land management, greater use of renewable resources and by reducing the rate of land use change from urban sprawl and new development; • sustainably manage waste generation, invest in different types of waste treatment and support circular economy principles, prioritising prevention, reuse, recycling and recovery, to support a healthy environment, economy and society.
Specific Measures	<p>Already in 2002, Ireland introduced a levy on plastics bags which reduced their usage with 90 per cent in 10 years.</p> <p>In the field of Green Public Procurement, Ireland adopted the “Guidance for the Public Sector” (2014). The document was developed to assist the public sector to implement and maintain procedures for green public procurement. It explicitly addresses numerous criteria concerning requirements for plastic components or packaging.</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities	Local authorities
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	EPR systems

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Greek market declare the conformity to the following standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• EN 13427• EN 13428• EN 13429• EN 13430• EN 13431• EN 13432	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	Producers and importers SHALL subscribe to one producer responsibility organizations (PRO) accredited: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• REPAK, in which the submission fee is dependent on the type and weight of packaging or to an autonomous accredited (self-compliance)	

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• REPAK
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to REPAK members

Penalties

	Details
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Luxembourg

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	The country has recently released the "Plan National De Gestion Des Dechets et Des Ressources" (2018), a roadmap of sorts highlighting issues and drawing out concrete plans to facilitate the transition to a circular economy, covering also specific issues such as waste valorization, enhanced separate collection, measures for plastic carrier bags

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities	EPR systems, Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	EPR systems, Companies (Packaging waste producers)/Operators

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Luxembourgish market declare the conformity to the following standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	Producers and importers SHALL subscribe to one producer responsibility organizations (PRO) accredited: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VALORLUX, in which the submission fee is dependent on the type and weight of packaging or to an autonomous accredited (self-compliance)	

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Labelling

Details	
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">VALORLUX
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">"Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to VALORLUX members

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

The Netherlands

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>The Netherlands adopted the circular economy programme From Waste to Resource (2014). It formulates specific measures and objectives to enable the transition from a linear to a circular economy.</p> <p>The Country relies on the Government Programme for a Circular Economy by 2050 (2016), which captures all government policy efforts on circular economy, resource efficiency and raw materials. This document presents a vision of a future-proof, sustainable economy. The ambition is to realise an interim objective of a 50% reduction in the use of primary raw materials (minerals, fossil-based materials and metals) by 2030. In addition, it includes additional measures and sets a course for the way to 2050. The plastic sector lies among the 5 priority sectors of the Programme.</p> <p>The National Bioeconomy Strategy (2018) highlights the vision of the Country about the subject.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>As a priority sector for the Programme for a Circular Economy by 2050, a Transition Agenda on Plastics Goals for 2030 is developed.</p> <p>The Strategic goals highlighted are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plastic products are designed in such a manner as to enable reuse and high-grade recycling after being discarded; • plastic materials in value chains are utilised as efficiently as possible, which would lead to a reduction in the need for raw materials and the prevention of “leakage” in the system; • optimisation of the renewable use of plastic material flows, by large-scale usage of plastic recyclates and biobased plastics, making use of biodegradable plastics in specific situations in which such plastics have added value for the circular economy (more effective joint processing with biotic residues; pollution risks for the marine environment). <p>The Plastic Value Chain Agreement – under the same Programme - forms a link between existing and new activities, guides parties' activities and specific Green Deals that have been signed and implemented or are yet to be signed and guides the relevant sectoral innovation contracts. It links the activities of parties that wish to promote the fact that plastics and plastic products contribute to a sustainable society.</p> <p>In addition, the Dutch government banned free plastic bags in most shops (2017).</p>

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	Local authorities, deposit system for recycle	EPR systems
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems, deposit system for recycle	EPR systems

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Dutch market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>For packaging products not covered by the beverages containers EPR system, producers and importers SHALL subscribe to the compliance scheme AFVALFONDS/NEDVANG, in which the submission fee is dependent on the type and weight of packaging.</p> <p>For single-use PET bottles with capacity higher than 1 litre a return scheme is implemented to increase recycling. A return scheme for single-use PET bottles with a capacity lower than 1 litre will be implemented on July 1st 2021.</p>	

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AFVALFONDS/NEDVANG

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Details

Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• “Green Dot”: voluntary use, allowed to AFVALFONDS/NEDVANG members• Disposal instructions from the disposal guide of KIDV (https://kidv.nl/disposal-guide)
--------------------	---

Penalties

Details

General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improper use of “Green Dot” registered trademark is punishable by the owner according to the related regulation of use.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Portugal

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>Portugal adopted a Circular Economy Action Plan, Leading the Transition: action for the circular economy in Portugal: 2017–2020 (2017). The Plan acts at multiple scales, from national to local. In addition, the issue of circular economy – being cross-sectoral - is covered by other Portuguese political domains.</p> <p>Moreover, work for the launch of the “Portuguese Bioeconomy Strategy Roadmap” is ongoing.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>Portugal introduced measures aimed at the more sustainable use of resources and the adoption of circular solutions in Public Administration (2018), promoting – among other – the reduction of plastic products consumption.</p> <p>Portugal was also the first EU country to ban single use fossil-based plastic products at the government, direct administration and public companies level (2019).</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse
Collection	Local authorities	Companies (Packaging waste producers)
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems	Companies (Packaging waste producers)

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version:	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Portuguese market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 <p>Producers and importers of specific products SHALL guarantee a given reuse rate, by demonstrating design suitable to containers return.</p>	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Producers and importers of non-reusable urban packaging waste SHALL subscribe to one of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sociedade Ponto Verde – SPV, a no profit organization in which the submission fee is dependent on the type and weight of packaging • Compliance scheme NOVO, a profit organization <p>or organize an autonomous system (self-compliance)</p>	<p>Commercial and industrial waste management is a service offered by waste management operators</p>

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPV
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Green Dot”: voluntary use, allowed to SPV members

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Penalties

Details	
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable with a fee of 0.50 € for each non-compliant unit of packaging

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Sweden

Main Policy Framework

Policy Framework	
General Measures	<p>Sweden has not adopted specific strategies or plans for the development of circular economy. The promotion of sustainable development is addressed within the Environmental Code (1999), which guarantees that reuse and recycling, as well as other management of materials, raw materials and energy, are encouraged so that natural cycles are established and maintained.</p> <p>More specific initiatives include the creation of the "Delegation for circular economy", as an advisory body to the government. The tasks of the delegation cover the preparation of a strategy for the delegation's work on a transition to a circular and bio-based economy, the connection between relevant actors in order to facilitate work and create synergies, being a knowledge centre and identifying obstacles, contradictory incentives, need for education and advice and suggest cost-effective measures. Moreover, the Innovation partnership programme – Circular and Bio-based Economy (2016) aimed to jointly mobilise innovation initiatives to ensure that the proportion of the bio-based economy grows and promote circular solutions.</p>
Specific Measures	<p>To reduce the consumption of plastic bags, Sweden has adopted the Regulation and guidance on plastic bags. In addition, plastic bottles for beverages must belong to an approved recycling system before being marketed in Sweden.</p>

Management Model & Responsibility Scheme

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Prevention	Companies (National producer and importer of goods), deposit system for reuse	Companies (National producer and importer of goods)
Collection	EPR systems, deposit system for recycle	EPR systems
Recycle and Recovery	EPR systems, deposit system for recycle	EPR systems

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Compliance of Business

	Urban Packaging Waste	Commercial & Industrial Packaging Waste
Environmental Impact	<p>All packaging shall be compliant with essential requirements on composition, reusability, recoverability (in particular, recyclability) if producers introducing packaged goods in the Sweden market declare the conformity to the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 13427 • EN 13428 • EN 13429 • EN 13430 • EN 13431 • EN 13432 	
Waste Collection, Recycle and Recovery	<p>Producers and importers of reusable PET containers for beverages SHALL subscribe to an accredited deposit system, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dela AB <p>Producers and importers of non-refillable containers for beverages SHALL subscribe to an accredited deposit system, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Returpack AB <p>Other producers and importers SHALL subscribe to the FTI compliance scheme, a no profit organization in which the submission fee is dependent on the type and weight of packaging</p>	

Labelling

	Details
Regulation	In compliance with Decision 129/97/CE: establishment of a system to identify packaging material according to Directive 94/62/CE
Accredited Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Returpack AB • FTI
Labels (& details)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Returpack", "PANT": compulsory for packaging subject to deposit • "Green Dot": voluntary use, allowed to FTI members

Penalties

	Details
General	Penalty measures can be imposed to obliged companies for missed subscription to foreseen management systems
Specific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improper use of "Green Dot" registered trademark is punishable with a fee of 0.50 € for each non-compliant unit of packaging

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

ANNEX B – CIRCPACK STAKEHOLDERS' CONSULTATION

Stakeholders Consultation

CIRC-PACK

Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

Grant agreement: 730423

From March 2017 to February 2020

Prepared by: RINA Consulting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730423.

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730423".

This document has been prepared by CIRC-PACK project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the EC-GA contract no 730423.

Neither Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of CIRC-PACK Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- (c) makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, expressed or implied,
 - (iv). with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, or
 - (v). that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property, or
 - (vi). that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- (d) assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if the Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the CIRC-PACK Project Consortium Agreement has been informed of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

INTRODUCTION

This consultation is part of the activities performed within the CIRC-PACK “Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain” project and, specifically, it is developed for the specific task of providing policy recommendations to overcome existing barriers for the recycling of fossil based and bio-based plastic for packaging.

The consultation is dedicated to educated participants, with experience in circular economy matters, plastic and packaging sectors and it is anonymous.

In details, it is organized into two main sections: Barriers and Measures.

Within the section “Barriers”, you will be asked to rate the importance of a number of barriers, organized according to the macro-issues they concern. The selection of barriers is intended to be representative of the existing perspectives to the issues hampering recycling of plastic and bio-plastic packaging products, but neither as exhaustive or as an in-depth list.

Then, within the section “Measures”, you will be questioned about the desirability and the Implementation of a selection of policy “Measures”.

Additional comments about each measure are very welcome to generate robust and consistent findings.

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Background information

A. Which title best describes you?

- Business representative organisation/trade body
- Packaging designer / manufacturer / converter
- Distributor / Retailer
- Waste Management Company / Reprocessor
- Local government
- Consultancy / Academic or research
- Individual
- Other
- If you answered 'Other' above, please provide details:.....

B. In which European country(ies) is your organization operating?

.....

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Barriers

Barriers to plastic and bio-plastic packaging circular economy				
General Legislative	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Absence of End of Waste criteria for plastic packaging waste				
Use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer				
Possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation				
Landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries				
Difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials				
Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging				
Supply chain	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs (Member States), preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging				
Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers				
Low capillarity of re-processing plants and logistic issues				

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Barriers to plastic and bio-plastic packaging circular economy

Economic	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice				
The cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues				
Lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging				
Material incineration – as a form of down-cycling of plastic packaging - can be cheaper than recycling				
Awareness / Engagement	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of plastic waste management				
Lack of citizens education about correct waste management				
Technology and Design	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling				
Many recycling processes are still not optimal, leading to a loss in material quality and quantity				
Nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process				
A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products				

Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Barriers to plastic and bio-plastic packaging circular economy				
Traceability and Standardization	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material				
Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion				
Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design				
Barriers Specific for Biobased, Biodegradable and Compostable Products	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
The meaning of “bioplastic” covers a variety of different materials, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both				
Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics and lack of efficient separate collection of bio-waste in MSs				
Lack of composting facilities that are able to treat all types of bio-waste (as defined by the WFD) and produce high quality compost				
Other Barriers	Very important	Important	Slightly important	Unimportant
Please describe below any additional barrier you consider relevant:				
Please describe below any additional barrier you consider relevant:				
Please describe below any additional barrier you consider relevant:				

Measures

RATIONALE: Technological gaps in collection, selection, treating and processing of Plastic Packaging Waste are registered across the MSs, including different implementation levels of the European legislation. Up to date, the lack of standards and coordination across the value chain has allowed the proliferation of materials, formats, labelling, collection schemes, and sorting and reprocessing systems, which collectively hamper the development of effective markets.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: The EU is constantly committed toward the definition of a common strategy towards sustainable waste management. Relevant examples of legislation currently in, include the Waste Directive, the Plastic Packaging Waste Directive and the Single Use Plastics Directive. Even though a Directive requires each MS to implement it, and it is not applicable as such, as for the case of a Regulation, it sets a common direction for the MSs.

Encourage collaboration between Member States, in order to align their approach and narrow the existing gaps as much as possible

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: From the analysis of documents and other references on the waste issues, it is evident that language and definitions represent a key barrier and at the same time a key driver to develop a structured and effective strategy on the plastic packaging waste policies

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: A simple way to overcome this issue would be to insert a glossary in each publication, in order to avoid potential forms of miscommunication and / or spreading of misleading information.

Guarantee use of a homogeneous terminology with respect to waste and waste management across different policies and different sectors

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer.

The meaning of "bioplastic" covers a variety of different materials, such as bio-based, biodegradable/compostable or both

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Green Public Procurement is a voluntary instrument that acts as driver and financial incentive, generating an important contribution to sustainable consumption and production. As a matter of fact, the economic significance of public procurement in Europe is considerable, involving around 14% of GDP in the EU on the purchase of services, works and supplies.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: The Danish municipality Lolland, recycling and recyclability criteria for packaging have been included in their tender for cleaning services: 75% of material used for bags must be recycled or biodegradable; non-reusable packaging must be easy to separate into single material types; monomaterials are to be used if possible; only recyclable materials must be used; and use of dark colours must be avoided.

In 2016, the City of Ghent established a four-year framework agreement for the supply of cleaning and polishing products. It was required that products in certain categories, including cleaning products and hygiene products (e.g. soap) met the criteria of the C2C 'Bronze' label or equivalent. As a result, the recycled content and recyclability of waste has greatly improved: packaging uses 85% recycled cardboard, plastic bottles made from polyethylene high-density (PEHD) are 100% recyclable and consist of 10% recycled PEHD, while those made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) are 100% recyclable and made from 81% recycled materials.

In 2013, the City of Turin introduced a number of measures to their school catering contract to enhance its sustainability, which included requiring the use of energy efficient appliances and low environmental impact transport, as well as significantly reducing packaging and waste, for example by using tap water instead of bottled water, and favouring reusable and refillable products where packaging is unavoidable. In addition, contractors were required to shift from using plastic to reusable dishes.

Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging materials that are easy to separate and recycle (e.g.: mono-material, limited number of detachable components, suitable for recycling or up-cycling)

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging - The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling - A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions including high rates of recycled content

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging, The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling, A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Green Procurement is a voluntary instrument that acts as driver and financial incentive, generating an important contribution to sustainable consumption and production. Its use should not be restricted to the public sector and should be also considered by private companies, especially the large ones, which can enforce a significant influence on multiple industrial segments

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Several international firms are currently promoting initiatives to improve the sustainability of their packaging products, including plastic. Eco-design is already being implemented in order to reduce material use and to increase the share of recycled content, for example by including secondary material as ocean plastic sourced from coastal areas. In addition, procurement standards and eco-label are used in some cases. In parallel, some firms are promoting the manufacturing of reusable or industrially compostable packaging in the near future.

Incentivize large actors to implement responsible and sustainability-oriented purchase and strategy choices, for example aligned with public procurement criteria

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging, Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design, a sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products.

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Fiscal tools, both at the national and regional level, can create economic incentives or deterrents for individuals to better sort their waste, and for private companies to invest in new technologies and enhance new product designs, which will improve the quantity and quality of recycled plastics.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Assuming that increasing the value of after-use plastic packaging reduces the likelihood that it escapes the collection system, AEMME Linea Ambiente (<https://www.aemmelineaambiente.it/>), a waste management company operating in a few towns in Northern Italy, introduced in 2016 a pilot innovative tariff scheme for households. The scheme includes a fixed share depending on the size of the property and a variable share, depending on the amount of unsorted waste generated, measured through tagged bags. In a short time span, the initiative produced impressive results in increasing the rates of sorted wastes.

Reward industrial stakeholders demonstrating promising circular business models for packaging waste through suitable EPR schemes, fiscal incentives or tax exemptions

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries, Lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice, The cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues, Lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging, A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Introduce incentives to guarantee that the most sustainable recycling routes are cost-effective compared with the other available options (e.g.: incineration)

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Material incineration – as a form of down-cycling of plastic packaging - can be cheaper than recycling

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Launch the establishment of waste management tariff schemes based on the amount of waste actually produced and on the quality of sorting achieved

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers, Lack of fiscal incentives at various levels, to promote practice such as better sorting, technological development and eco-design practice, Lack of citizens education about correct waste management

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Plastic packaging products and waste – especially if not correctly managed – are responsible for negative impacts in terms of degradation of natural systems due to leakage, impacts on land use, biodiversity and air quality, greenhouse gas emissions. These impacts are usually correlated to the primary feedstock used for packaging production.

A number of schemes aimed at incorporating such externalities into the full cost of end-products already exist, with the final aim of increasing recovery rates.

Among these schemes, the EU legislation sets out an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Scheme for end-of-life vehicles, batteries and accumulators, waste electrical and electronic good waste streams. EPR involves a shift in responsibility in the treatment of waste from the public authorities to manufacturers that are in charge of the treatment and disposal cost of the waste generated by their products. However, only few EPR schemes have developed mechanisms to lower the fees for eco-designed products and ensure that producer fees incentivize prevention, reparability and recyclability.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: France experienced a “bonus-malus” system, which increased charges to products containing materials disrupting the recycling process. However, the results of this “bonus-malus” system and its impacts on eco-design efforts are not known yet.

In 2016, the Italian CONAI Consortium for packaging approved the Plastic Packaging Contribution Diversification project. It provides the basis for the modulation of fees for plastic packaging according to environmental criteria. Given the complexity of plastics as a packaging material, the launch of the project aimed at promoting sortable and recyclable plastic packaging. Contribution levels are based on the environmental impact of products end-of-life. The proposed reductions depend on the recyclability and sortability of plastic packaging, as well as on the destination of packaging and packaging waste. The new approach introduced three new contribution diversifications on plastic packaging:

- Level A: sortable and recyclable packaging from the Commerce & Industry circuit
- Level B: sortable and recyclable packaging from the Household circuit
- Level C: packaging not sortable/recyclable with current technologies.

Promote eco-designed packaging solutions and waste prevention in packaging design within the EPR schemes, for example by introducing quantitative targets on such performances

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging,

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

RATIONALE: Countries with landfill restrictions of recyclable and recoverable waste have, on average, higher recycling rates of plastic post-consumer waste

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: In Austria, Germany, Netherlands, Denmark, Belgium, Luxembourg and Finland, landfill restriction on recyclable and recoverable wastes are in place. These countries present a minimum share of landfilled plastic-post consumer rates, and high rates of recycling (25%-45%) and energy recovery (55%-75%).

Introduce landfill bans or increase landfill costs in order to make recycle more cost effective and – in parallel – introduce incentives or tax exemptions to decrease the cost of recycle of certain plastic streams

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries, The cost of collection, sorting and recycling outweighs the generated revenues

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: MSs can stipulate trade agreements (e.g.: bilateral trade agreements, multilateral trade agreements) in order to improve and facilitate imports and exports. Doing so, the possibility to transfer a certain waste stream to recycling or recovering in another Country, where the recovery is technically feasible, increases.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Examples of Multilateral agreements between European MSs dealing with the carriage of packaging or waste are:

- M192 Carriage in packagings to which packing instruction P801 applies - Expired on 1 January 2009
- M268 Carriage of packagings, discarded, empty, uncleaned (UN 3509) - Expired on 1 January 2015
- M287 Carriage of certain wastes containing dangerous goods, signed by Austria, Czech Republic, Liechtenstein and Italy - Date of Expiry: Applies from 2 August 2015 up to 1 August 2020.

Furthermore, an excellent example of a European agreement on the Transport of materials with special characteristics is the European Agreement concerning international carriage of dangerous goods by road (ADR). ADR, by the French Accord européen relatif au transport International des marchandises dangereuses par Route, is the European Agreement on the International Transport of dangerous Goods by road, signed in Geneva on 30 September 1957 and ratified in Italy by law 12 August 1962 N. 1839.

Facilitate negotiating mechanisms for trade agreements that allow to increase recovery rates, to reduce recovery tariffs and to accelerate materials import and export

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials, Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging, Low capillarity of re-processing plants and logistic issues

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: The encouragement of a wide stakeholder group, including designers - that play a critical role along the entire product value chain - and policymakers, who can trigger progress in the near term, is important to generate a system shift to circular economy in the plastic packaging sector. Numerous studies have also highlighted the lack of full harmonisation of collection and recovery systems for packaging as a relevant concern for the implementation of circular value chains for packaging products in the EU. This lack of harmonisation could result in internal market disruptions in particular in cases of parallel trade or private imports in border regions.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: The European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform is a virtual open space, which aims at promoting Europe's transition to a circular economy by facilitating policy dialogue among stakeholders and by disseminating activities, information, and good practices on the circular economy. Stakeholders can take part in the Platform by participating in the annual conference and by interacting on the website to look for good practices, to engage with other stakeholders and to share their own good practices and events.

Similarly, in May 2016, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation launched the New Plastics Economy initiative – an ambitious global programme, which has secured over USD 10 million funding to date and involves over 40 key stakeholders across the value chain – to accelerate the shift to a New Plastics Economy.

Boost networking initiatives for industrial stakeholders committed to the achievement of a circular and sustainable economy for plastic packaging and their connection with other industrial sectors

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of plastic waste management

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Awareness raising initiatives are a consolidated instrument to spread knowledge about the challenges of the plastics economy and on how to address them along the entire value chains. These initiatives may play a crucial role especially in educating citizens, which play a key role in the collection and sorting of plastic packaging waste and municipal waste in general. Indeed, packaging waste is often varied in composition, may be multi-material and contaminated with other materials (e.g. organics). This complicates material sorting, resulting in mixed packaging streams being collected, often with high levels of contamination, both in terms of 'non-target' polymers and contamination with other materials. In addition, the situation is complicated by the presence of bioplastics products, which, due to their similar appearance, cannot be easily differed from conventional plastic products.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: An Italian initiative (<http://www.dicheplastica6.it/iniziativa/>) is aimed at favouring and promoting good practices for packaging waste management, including bio-based plastic packaging through the realization of tutorials and through the publication of technical information.

Other awareness raising campaigns are being developed by regional and local authorities, including, for example:

- online games such as Don't Feed Simon;
- theatre performance and sketches to explain the ban of plastic bags;
- campaigns in local newspapers and social media;
- cleaning beaches/rivers days at schools.

Also for bio-based products, both official and non-official references aimed at improving waste management exist. The standards EN 13432 "Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation" and EN 14995, describing the same requirements not only for packaging, but for plastics in general, define the technical specification for the compostability of bioplastics products. In addition, a number of labels for industrially compostable products and for home compostability exist.

Increase consumers' awareness about packaging design, properties and values through standardized labels, including on products precise statements about the presence of multi-material packaging, separable packaging parts, biobased material

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Lack of citizens education about correct waste management, Nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process, Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion, Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Increase consumers' awareness about the importance of implementing virtuous waste management practices and increase guidance on sorting procedures available in their area, in order to increase the level of separation and to increase the overall quality and efficiency of the recycling process

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Lack of citizens education about correct waste management, Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion, Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Complex packaging designs exist, with commonly little regard for end-of-life sorting and recycling. Plastic packaging is often made from one or more different polymers, depending on its purpose, in order to combine functional properties to meet production and use requirements. In some other cases, such complexity is solely marketing and brand driven (e.g. black trays for meat and ready meals; gloss finishes; pack clarity for beverages).

In such context, the current Ecodesign Directive (2009/125/EC) aims to make new products more energy efficient. In 2018, the European Parliament has called to go beyond energy efficiency and consider other aspects in the design of new products, such as how long a product lasts, how easy it is to take apart, repair and recycle.

More In detail, Annex II of Directive 94/62/EC on Packaging and Packaging Waste includes a list of Essential Requirements on the composition and the reusable and recoverable, including recyclable, nature of packaging. However, criteria have been recently discussed as they may be too loose to guarantee effective implementation of eco-design principles, which are difficult to enforce.

Criteria include, e.g.:

- “Packaging shall be so manufactured that the packaging volume and weight be limited to the minimum adequate amount to maintain the necessary level of safety, hygiene and acceptance for the packed product and for the consumer”;
- “Packaging shall be designed, produced and commercialized in such a way as to permit its reuse or recovery, including recycling, and to minimize its impact on the environment when packaging waste or residues from packaging waste management operations are disposed of”.

Interesting areas for improvement include the design of type and size of packaging formats compatible with existing technology used for recycling, also aiming at limiting the variety of products to be processed in existing plants and the effective enforcement of eco-design criteria and schemes to ensure and demonstrate which products are compliant.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Design improvements can be realized by acting on format design, polymer selection, pigment and additive choice. Examples include design choices relating to: labels, inks, direct printing, glues, shape of the packaging, replacing PVC in packaging applications by more common polymers.

Within CIRCPACK project, Demo Case B involves the production of two eco-designs. Firstly, a multi-material packaging is developed; a detergent box which consists of board and plastic. This design aimed for recyclability in the paper recycling process and was tested with positive results.

There are also examples of international firms which explicitly chose to limit colouring of packaging to enable recycling

Promote design best practices and guidelines across the plastic packaging manufacturing industry

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products, Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Introduce more stringent Essential Requirements for packaging products to be put on the market and establish control schemes to ensure compliance of products with such requirements

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling, A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Recycling is often hampered by the lack of technological solutions either for certain polymers, products or by the lack of an insufficient quality of the secondary raw material. In this context, it would be important to continue developing reprocessing technologies to enable the recycling of materials that cannot be processed into high-quality products today and improve the quality of secondary raw material to allow for more subsequent loops.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Within Demo Case C of the CIRCPACK project, existing sorting and recycling processes are enhanced through new monitoring systems and technologies, increasing recovery rates and ensuring quality and reliability of the recovered materials to be reinserted in the same value chain - thereby closing the loop.

In 2017, Fater SpA presented the first plant able to recycle 100% of used AHP. The plant is operating by a waste operator who transforms input waste into three different value added secondary raw materials, namely plastic, cellulose and superabsorbent polymer. Efficient recycling service for the fraction of used personal absorbent products at home, by using sealed containers in which used diapers can be disposed of. For this project, Fater Spa has been awarded as "circular economy" champion by Legambiente, in support of an ambitious agreement on the reform of European waste policy.

Encourage and incentivize research and technological development for recycling techniques and technologies, including improvement of mechanical recycling and up-scaling of chemical recycling technologies

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging, Low capillarity of re-processing plants and logistic issues, The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling, Many recycling processes are still not optimal, leading to a loss in material quality and quantity, Actual realization of compostability for related products is often possible only under controlled conditions (e.g. in industrial composters)

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Different factors must be considered where local and regional authorities decide to improve separate collection systems of plastic waste, such as the size and density of population in the geographical area concerned and the related socioeconomic conditions.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: In highly populated regions, with multiple socio-economic communities, post collection treatment can be efficient in terms of quantity of plastic recycled. On the other hand, for poorly populated areas, door-to-door collection combined with a unit-based pricing is probably the most effective way to improve the collection.

Promote research to structure the most effective waste management system (e.g.: collection, sorting at plant, sorting at consumers) in relation with citizens' awareness level, urban geographical context, available technologies, etc.

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers, Nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process, Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: A prerequisite for increased performance and investments in the recycling chain is the existence of a demand capable of absorbing the outputs of the recycling facilities. However, it happens that secondary raw material is not absorbed because it does not meet the requirements of the manufacturing industry.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: As a general good practice, it is recorded that the implementation of a selective waste management system at source lowers the risk of organic-substance contamination of waste streams and it improves the quality of materials along the value chain.

In addition, a way to improve transparency would be to use a software tool or platform, to match both recycler and companies that source recycled content. A successful example of this kind of initiative is the US Materials Marketplace pilot that involved 23 participating companies and identified 2.4 million tonnes of underutilised materials. The set-up included a technical team actively looking for synergy opportunities among the participants: 68 synergy opportunities were identified and several business-to-business transactions were underway or being explored. Following the success of the pilot phase, further expansion of the platform is planned.

As a successful example of improving the issue of waste traceability and consequently quality of waste streams for re-processing, the non-profit waste management organization TRACIMAT (<http://www.tracimat.be/>), founded by the Flemish Construction Confederation to improve traceability for Construction&Demolition waste can be cited. TRACIMAT promotes traceability by issuing a "certificate of selective demolition" for construction and demolition waste that has been selectively collected and subsequently gone through a tracing system. The demolition certificate tells the processor whether the demolition waste can be accepted as "low environmental risk material" and therefore be processed separately from waste streams with a high environmental risk.

Increase transparency in waste traceability, by encouraging municipalities or entities responsible for waste management to create robust datasets for each waste streams and by introducing certificates of waste treatments performed and source of waste material

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers, Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material, Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Introduce minimum requirements for secondary raw material specifications and labels

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging, Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers, Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material, Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion, Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

RATIONALE: The purpose of end-of-waste criteria is to avoid confusion about the waste definition and to clarify when certain waste that has undergone recovery ceases to be waste. Recycling should be supported by creating legal certainty and an equal level playing field and by removing unnecessary administrative burdens.

The Commission published in 2013 the Technical proposal developed by JRC-IPTS on EoW Criteria for biodegradable waste subjected to biological treatment (compost & digestate). In 2014, EoW for the Packaging Waste Plastics stream is analysed within the JRC Technical Report entitled "EoW Criteria for waste plastic for conversion". This technical report defines a possible set of EoW criteria, developing a comprehensive techno-economic analysis of the waste plastic production chain and an analysis of the economic, environmental and legal impacts when such waste plastic ceases to be waste.

Nevertheless, further steps towards the adoption of the criteria have not been taken so far.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: The activities and actions of the Italian companies Fater SpA (producer of absorbent hygiene products and owner of a recycling plant equipped with technologies suitable for their recycling) and Contarina (waste management company) lead to the recent adoption (May 2019) of a national end-of-waste criterion for AHP items, which can now be fully recycled to produce secondary polyolefinic plastics, cellulose and superabsorbent polymers.

Define EoW for fossil plastic waste streams

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Absence of End of Waste criteria for plastic packaging waste, Possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation, Difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials, Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

Define EoW for bio-plastic waste streams

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Absence of End of Waste criteria for plastic packaging waste, Possible inconsistencies concerning the interaction between waste legislation and substances and raw material legislation, Difficulties in establishing agreements to import&export waste materials or secondary raw materials, Incompatibility of recovered waste requirements of the manufacturing industries, due to insufficient quality and lack of detailed information about the secondary raw material

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: A change in the perception of quality and performance of products manufactured from recycled materials, as well as an improved awareness about environmental impacts along the life cycle of a product, can support in closing the loop for plastic packaging products. Labels may support this cultural shift, by communicating recycled content, possible end-of-life routes, etc.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: In 2017, the European Commission launched the revised EU Ecolabel criteria for six widely used types of detergents (i.e.: laundry, industrial laundry, dishwasher, industrial dishwasher, hand dishwashing and hard-surface cleaning detergents). The EU Ecolabel certifies the awarded detergents are free from microplastics and their packaging meet strict requirements. The EU Ecolabel help consumers and companies to choose products that have a lower environmental impact throughout their lifecycle in the framework of the Commission's flagship circular economy package.

Promote environmental labels and product declaration for packaging product, covering the entire life cycle

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Use of misleading and confusing information about packaging properties and environmental burdens, including vocabulary misuse, hampering the implementation of best practices for consumer, Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging, Lack of standardized and homogeneous implementation of schemes (e.g.: EPR schemes, deposit schemes) to value environmental negative impacts of plastic packaging, Lack of awareness across the actors involved in the value chain about system thinking, environmental impacts and benefits of plastic waste management, A sustainable end of life is not the main design criteria for plastic packaging products, Fragmented development and adoption of labelling standards, hindering public understanding and creating confusion, Low demand of secondary raw materials resulting partly from the lack of standards requiring resource efficient product design,

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Today's plastics industry is defined by a fossil-based feedstock and energy paradigm, structured in a well consolidated and long standing scheme. Thus, despite many efforts at European, national and local level, scale-up and commercialisation of bio-based feedstock or completely novel (plastic) materials remains rather limited.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: Under Demo Case A of the CIRC PACK project, biomaterials with properties in line with the correspondent final product requirements are produced. This bio-materials are expected to prove performances at least equal to existing comparable packaging material. The produced biomaterials will be used for the manufacturing of trays, bottles, coffee capsules, jars, films and pallets.

Under Demo Case B of the CIRCPACK project, a multilayer packaging is developed; a film seal for trays (of fresh chicken) which consists of multiple layers of plastic. This design is aimed at biodegradability and compostability. The separate components were also tested with positive results and it is expected that the multilayer as a whole will be biodegradable and compostable.

Within the proposal for Directive, "on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment," the European Commission has come up with measures banning or restricting the use of single-use plastic application (such as plates, cutlery, cups, plastic bags, etc.). This proposal does not directly address questions of product policy and choices of materials substituting plastic. However, indirectly, by taking of some products of the market and reducing others, the proposal will create important opportunities for innovative solutions on material substitution and substitution of single-use plastic products, as well as for new business models and systems for re-use.

Promote research on new value chains and products for bio-plastic materials

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging, Inefficacy of collection and sorting integrated process, preventing economies of scale and the delivery of consistent, high-quality material streams to recyclers, The variety of plastic packaging products on the market (e.g.: multi-material packaging, bioplastic products, small-format items) is not reflected in the variety and the performance of technologies for sorting and recycling, Nutrient-contamination of packaging, in form of organic residues or odours makes it difficult to efficiently separate the packaging in the recycling process, Difficulties in the organic waste stream selection for bioplastic caused by accidental flow of conventional plastics, Actual realization of compostability for related products is often possible only under controlled conditions (e.g. in industrial composters)

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

Ban certain traditional fossil-based plastic products and – in parallel – facilitate the commercialization of innovative equivalent bio-based compostable products

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Landfill restrictions or other similar measures are not implemented in some countries, Existence of socio-technological gaps among MSs, preventing the growth of a single market for circular plastic and bio-plastic packaging

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

RATIONALE: Green Public Procurement is a voluntary instrument that acts as driver and financial incentive, generating an important contribution to sustainable consumption and production. As a matter of fact, the economic significance of public procurement in Europe is considerable, involving around 14% of GDP in the EU on the purchase of services, works and supplies.

EXAMPLE OF BEST PRACTICE: In 2016, the Public Procurement Working Group of the European Commission's Expert Group for Bio-based Products published 15 recommendations for an increased uptake of bio-based products in public procurement programs. The 15 recommendations include promotional campaigns targeting specific materials, regions and sectors, the roll-out of standards and labels, benchmarking and goal setting, but also manifesto definition, targeted outreach and general communication, technical support to procurers, as well as intervention on legislation if and where possible. The Expert Group identified multiple areas for action to help grow such a large and diverse sector.

Introduce Green Public Procurement requirements to reward packaging solutions based on bioplastics

ADDRESSED BARRIERS: Poor systematic implementation of Green Public Procurement guidelines promoting circular economy schemes for plastic packaging

How would you consider the implementation of this measure?

- Very desirable
- Desirable
- Undesirable
- Very undesirable

Which would be the most suitable recipient policy of this measure?

(more than one option may be chosen)

- EU legislation
- National legislation
- Regional / local legislation

If you wish, please provide further details

.....

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

ANNEX C – EU CONSULTATION “FUTURE CLIMATE AND ENERGY POLICY - A STRATEGY FOR LONG-TERM EU GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS REDUCTIONS”, ON BEHALF OF CIRCPACK

Future climate and energy policy - a Strategy for long-term EU greenhouse gas emissions reductions

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Introduction

Climate change is happening and without further global action to mitigate it, temperatures will rise within this century well beyond a 2°Celsius compared to pre-industrial times. This will have major impacts on our economies and societies. In order to prevent this, 178 global partners cooperating under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) have ratified the Paris Agreement that calls upon all countries to keep global temperature increase to well below 2°C, and to pursue efforts to limit the increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. Parties to the Paris Agreement are to communicate by 2020 their long-term low greenhouse gas emission development strategies.

In March, the European Council invited the Commission to present a proposal for a strategy for long-term EU greenhouse gas emissions reductions in accordance with the Paris Agreement, taking into account the national plans. The European Parliament made a similar request.

The EU is on track to achieve its [2020 targets](#) and is currently putting in place policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% in 2030 and achieve high level of ambition in energy efficiency and renewable energy (the so called energy and climate framework for 2030). The policies, legislative instruments and support programmes from the European budget will put the EU on a trajectory compatible with the Paris Agreement, but further measures are needed for the time after 2030.

The EU has currently an objective in the context of necessary reductions by developed countries as a group, to reduce emissions by 80-95% by 2050 compared to 1990 levels.

Delivering the Paris Agreement will require a worldwide transition towards a global economy that will not further affect the climate in the second half of the century.

To pursue these latter objectives, the EU's long term strategy should put forward a vision for the mid-century and how the European Union can help protect the planet, defend its people and empower its economy. The EU's new long term strategy should describe economy-wide pathways with various options for decarbonisation and their implications on technology choices and socioeconomic factors.

The strategy will reflect on a long-term vision of a modern European economy working for all Europeans. Studies and stakeholder input will contribute to the formulation of this vision and help explain the choices to be made. The strategy should reflect on the essential opportunities and challenges stemming from the

long-term decarbonisation and clean energy transition of the EU:

- modernising the economy;
- improving citizens' quality of life;
- ensuring fair transition and tackling social challenges;
- reindustrialising Europe through digital, circular and low carbon innovation and clean mobility;
- promoting free, fair and sustainable global competition for markets, trade and investments; and
- maintaining the EU's global leadership position on key geostrategic and security issues.

The strategy will analyse cost-efficient scenarios towards decarbonisation in line with the Paris Agreement underpinned by holistic analysis of transition options across all key sectors of the economy. This includes a wide variety of sectors, starting with the central role of energy, buildings, transport and mobility, industrial production and the provision of services, waste, agriculture and land-use, as well as the use of natural resources. It will examine the potential and implications of the deployment of innovative technologies, sectoral integration, and of facilitating alternative choices for consumers. It will examine implications for security of supply, investments, competitiveness and socio-economic factors, such as economic growth and job creation, also considering the impacts on citizens, businesses. Regions that stand to be negatively affected by decarbonisation should be supported making this transition just and socially fair.

The visions and reflections of stakeholders involved from all sectors of the economy and society on how to reach the EU's ambition will be an important input into this process. Therefore, the European Commission is very much interested in your views on a strategy for long-term greenhouse gas emissions reductions for the European Union. Please take a moment to fill in our questionnaire. We welcome contributions from the general public, stakeholders and authorities alike. Your views will help to enrich our assessment of what the EU should do in order to meet its commitment under the Paris Agreement.

Guidance on the questionnaire

After a few introductory questions related to your general profile in section 1, the questionnaire has a number of questions in section 2.

To participate in the public consultation you are not obliged to fill in all questions. The different sections include questions on greenhouse gas reductions, the impact of consumers, the economic activity, energy, forests and land use, education and research, financing, meta trends, actors and adaptation to climate change. The final section is technical and more focussed on sectoral stakeholders (industry, transport, agriculture, land use).

Some questions are multiple choice questions. Other questions are open to which you can add if you want your comments. Please keep comments clear and concise because there is a limit on the number of characters you can enter.

If you want to express your views in more detail you can also upload a document with your views and insights.

As the results will be published on the Internet, please read the specific privacy statement attached to this consultation. It informs you about how your personal data and contribution will be dealt with. In the interest of transparency, if you are replying on behalf of an organisation, please register with the register of interest representatives if you have not already done so. Registering commits you to complying with a Code of Conduct. If you do not wish to register, your contribution will be treated and published together with those received from individuals.

General information about respondents

* In what capacity are you completing this questionnaire?

- as an individual in your personal capacity
- in your professional capacity or on behalf of an organisation

* Please give your name if replying as an individual/private person, otherwise give the name of your organisation:

Text of 3 to 100 characters will be accepted

We reply as CIRC-PACK Consortium (H2020 project under GA No 730423), on behalf of its 22 partners

Email address:

info@circpack.eu

* For individuals, country of residence; for professionals, headquarters and main country of operations:

Other

* If other, please specify:

Text of 3 to 100 characters will be accepted

CIRC-PACK partners come from 6 EU countries: Croatia, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Netherlands + Turkey

* Type of organisation (please select the answer option that fits best):

- Private enterprise
- Professional consultancy, law firm, self-employed consultant
- Trade, business or professional association
- Non-governmental organisation, platform or network
- Research and academia
- Social partners
- National, regional or local authority (mixed)
- Other

* If other, please specify:

Text of 3 to 100 characters will be accepted

5 non-profit on sustainable development, 2 municipalities, 3 RTOs, 8 large companies and 4 SMEs.

Please indicate the economic sector you are active in (as an individual or as an organisation)

- Agriculture, Hunting and Forestry
- Financial Intermediation
- Fishing
- Real Estate, Renting and Business Activities
- Mining and Quarrying
- Public Administration and Defence;
- Manufacturing
- Education
- Electricity, Gas and Water Supply
- Health and Social Work
- Construction
- Other Community, Social and Personal Services
- Wholesale and Retail Trade:
- Activities of Private Households as Employers
- Hotels and Restaurants
- Extraterritorial Organisations and Bodies
- Transport, Storage and Communications
- Other

* If other, please specify:

Text of 3 to 100 characters will be accepted

The Consortium is built across the plastic packaging waste value chain (www.circpack.eu)

* If you are a civil society organisation or a public administration, please indicate your main area of focus or your area of competence:

Text of 3 to 100 characters will be accepted

CIRC-PACK involve two municipalities in charge of waste management: Kartal-Turkey and Rijeka-Croatia

What size does your organisation have?

- Micro or small enterprise (10-49 persons employed)
- Medium-sized enterprise (50 - 249 persons employed)
- Large enterprise (250 or more persons employed)

If your organisation is registered in the Transparency Register, please give your Register ID number:

20 character(s) maximum

If your organisation is not registered, you can [register now](#).

* Please indicate your preference for the publication of your response on the Commission's website:

- Under the name given: I consent to publication of all information in my contribution and I declare that none of it is subject to copyright restrictions that prevent publication

- Anonymously: I consent to publication of all information in my contribution and I declare that none of it is subject to copyright restrictions that prevent publication
- Not at all — please keep my contribution confidential (it will not be published, but will be used internally within the Commission)

(Please note that regardless the option chosen, your contribution may be subject to a request for access to documents under [Regulation 1049/2001](#) on public access to European Parliament, Council and Commission documents. In this case the request will be assessed against the conditions set out in the Regulation and in accordance with applicable [data protection rules](#).)

Questions

Long term greenhouse gas emissions reductions

To achieve its temperature objectives, the Paris Agreement also includes a long term ambition to achieve a balance between emissions and removals of greenhouse gases by human activities in the second half of this century. Given that addressing climate change is a global challenge requiring all parties of the Paris Agreement to act, what do you think the EU should contribute to achieve the Paris Agreement's objectives:

- Reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the EU by 80% by 2050 compared to 1990 levels
- Reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the EU more, within the range of 80 to 95% by 2050 compared to 1990 levels
- Achieve already a balance between emissions and removals in the EU by 2050

In your opinion, what are the biggest opportunities and challenges

1000 character(s) maximum

Consumers

Next to the deployment of available and forthcoming technologies, when looking at the long term, consumer choices also have a key role in achieving the decarbonisation of our economy. Please fill in this section based on your habits if you are an individual or, if you are from an organisation, considering the organisation practice.

In your opinion, where do you expect the largest changes to happen in your daily life in order to meet the climate change challenge?

- Housing
- Mobility
- Food
- Consumer goods and services

Housing and offices

Energy consumption

To which extent would you support the following options that allow reducing the energy consumption and related CO₂ emissions in buildings?

Improving further the energy performance (insulation, triple glazing, etc.) of your building?

- Yes, I already have done it
- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, I rent
- No, too expensive
- No, other reason
- No opinion / I do not know

Installing heating and water boilers that run on renewables?

- Yes, I already have done it
- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, I rent
- No, too expensive
- No, other reason
- No opinion / I do not know

Installing heating and cooling equipment and use electric appliances with the best energy performance label?

- Yes, I already have done it
- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, I rent
- No, too expensive
- No, other reason
- No opinion / I do not know

Buying carbon free electricity or generating your own renewable electricity?

- Yes, I already have done it
- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, I rent

- No, too expensive
- No, other reason
- No opinion / I do not know

Having a smart meter and consuming electricity mostly when prices are low?

- Yes, I already have done it
- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, for privacy concern
- No, I do not want to change my consumption habits
- No, other reason
- No opinion / I do not know

Domestic waste

Do you sort your waste (paper, plastics, glass, metal, glass, organic...)?

- Yes
- No
- I do not see the interest

What would make you increase the separation of waste (paper, plastics, glass, metal, glass, organic...)?

- Adapted infrastructure (containers, etc.)
- Awareness campaign
- Financial incentives such as deposit schemes
- Other

* If other, please specify:

Text of 3 to 200 characters will be accepted

Results from CIRC-PACK survey - Main obstacles: inconvenience of several waste bins at home and distance to waste bring-points. Absence of door-to-door collection and lack of information come next.

Do you think increased recycling and reuse are important to achieve greenhouse gas reductions?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Mobility

To which extent would you support the following options that allow reducing the energy consumption and related CO₂ emissions?

Buying a vehicle that does not run on petrol or diesel (for instance an electric car)?

- Yes
- Yes, but only if not more expensive than conventional petrol or diesel cars

- Yes, but only if sufficient refuelling infrastructure is available
- No

Considering using car sharing services?

- Yes
- Yes, but only if an easy to use and affordable service is in place
- No

For short trips, avoiding private car and rather using public transport?

- Yes
- Yes but only if an accessible and regular service is in place
- No, because they are too slow
- No, because it is too expensive
- No

For short trips, avoiding private car and rather using (electric) bike or other active mobility modes?

- Yes
- Yes, but only if proper bike lanes are in place
- No

For longer distance, avoiding flights or car whenever an alternative is available?

- Yes
- Yes, provided a convenient alternative is in place
- No, too slow
- No, too expensive
- No, other reason

Do you think better urban planning would reduce the use of private cars and reduce congestion in the urban areas?

- Yes
- Yes, if combined with better public transport
- Yes, but difficult to put in place
- No

Do you think using more IT tools such as tele-working or video-conferencing could reduce mobility needs?

- Yes
- Yes, to some extent
- No, as difficult to put in place
- No

Food

Food production, processing and delivery have an impact on greenhouse gas emissions and natural resources consumption.

Would you consider it important that further awareness raising is undertaken about the impact of various types of food consumption on climate?

- Yes
- No

Would you consider the impact of food on greenhouse gas emissions when buying it?

- Yes
- Yes, if information is available about the carbon intensity of food
- Not if more expensive
- No

Also taking into account the importance to have a balanced diet for health purposes, would you consider changing to a less carbon intensive food diet (e.g. reduce red meat consumption)?

- Yes
- No
- I would require more information before changing my diet

Consumer goods and services

The products/services you consume and the way they are produced also impact energy consumption and related greenhouse gas emissions.

Do you ever consider the impact on greenhouse gas emissions when buying and consuming a product or services?

- Yes I do so regularly
- Yes but I often lack the information to do so
- No, I don't consider this

Would you consider buying products and services from companies that produce their goods and services in a greenhouse gas neutral manner?

- Yes
- No, if more expensive
- No, other
- No opinion / I do not know

Your work and your economic sector

For both individuals and organisations, details on the economic sector should be provided in Section 1.

Employment and a socially fair transition

In the coming decades, the transition to a low carbon economy will impact even more how we work and how we produce goods and services. Which statements below correspond in your opinion to the impact of climate change and the low carbon transition in your working environment?

Do you expect your company to create or reduce jobs due to the low-carbon transition?

- Create
- Reduce
- No opinion / I do not know

What could affect your job most in the future?

- The low carbon transition
- Digitalisation
- Impact of globalisation
- Socio-economic policies (for instance fiscal policy)
- Other

Do you think you or the sector you are active in would benefit from training of staff in the context of the energy and low carbon economy transformation?

- Yes
- Yes, to some extent
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

The impact of the low carbon transition on your sector

Do you consider the low carbon transition as an opportunity or as a challenge for your sector?

- An opportunity
- A challenge
- Both
- None
- No opinion / I do not know

Indicate by how much your sector could reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 compared to today?

- It cannot reduce
- Up to half
- By more than half
- Can decarbonise entirely
- No opinion / I do not know

What would be the preferred route to reduce these emissions in your sector?

- Further electrify
- Use other low carbon fuels, like hydrogen
- Improve to the maximum energy efficiency
- Circular economy, including recycling and re-use
- Development of new products and business concepts
- Other
- No opinion / I do not know

Will you (or your sector) invest in new low-carbon technologies?

- Yes, as a priority
- Yes, but not as a priority
- No, it has already invested enough
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

Do you think your sector could be further integrated with others so as to decrease emissions while increasing overall efficiency?

- Yes
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

Do you think the low carbon transition will lead the EU economy to:

- Modernise and reinforce its competitiveness
- Modernise, and reinforce its competitiveness, but only if non-EU countries and regions also engage in the transition towards a low carbon economy
- Lose competitiveness
- No opinion / I do not know

Do you think the low carbon transition can help the EU industry modernise and grow?

- Yes
- Yes, but only with public support
- Yes, but only if non-EU countries and regions also engage in the transition towards a low carbon economy
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

How can opportunities and challenges (in particular related to carbon intensive sectors or regions) be addressed? What key economic transformations should the EU pursue to achieve a low carbon and resilient economy?

1000 character(s) maximum

In the legislative framework on circular economy, when technological feasibility is proved, a great challenge is to overcome the legislative barriers in the valorisation of waste as secondary material, such as the case of plastics. The MS can use national waste reduction targets, keeping or introducing economic instruments as well as marketing restrictions, with intrinsic effects on decarbonization. One opportunity is the application of EoW criteria for PPW: common policies can control proprieties and safety of imported goods from non-EU states or between the MS. In this way it's possible to define how and when a material ends to be waste and become again a resource, resolving gaps, increasing the quantity of recovered waste and the related trade, improving the functioning of the internal market, and thus avoiding GHG emissions from use of primary resources. Besides, the opportunity to promote biobased materials should be further addressed, for replacement of fossil-based resources.

Energy

The energy system today is responsible for ca. 75% of the EU's greenhouse gases emissions and undergoes a rapid transition due to e.g. cost reduction of renewables, improvements of energy-efficiency

and rapid development of new technologies (e.g. batteries) driven i.a. by policies put forward by the EU and its Member States. Accelerating this change will play a central role in the transition of our economy towards a carbon-neutral economy.

In the following table listing different energy technologies, please rank each option in the table below from 1 (important) to 5 (not important) on what role you think they will play in the clean energy transition (not all options need to be ranked)?

	1	2	3	4	5
Energy efficiency reducing the need to produce energy	<input type="radio"/>				
Renewable energy from wind, solar or hydro	<input type="radio"/>				
Other forms of renewable energy, like geothermal, wave or tidal	<input type="radio"/>				
Nuclear energy	<input type="radio"/>				
Fossil fuels with Carbon Capture and Sequestration	<input type="radio"/>				
Solid biomass for heat and electricity production	<input type="radio"/>				
Advanced Liquid Biofuels	<input type="radio"/>				
Biogas from agricultural and domestic waste	<input type="radio"/>				
Electricity storage (e.g. batteries)	<input type="radio"/>				
Hydrogen (produced in a carbon-neutral manner)	<input type="radio"/>				
E-fuels derived from hydrogen	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

What are the biggest opportunities, including for the wider economy? What are the biggest challenges, including as regards public acceptance or the availability of land and natural resources, related to these future developments?

2000 character(s) maximum

The role of Forests and Land Use

Today, EU's forests, agriculture and land absorb more CO₂ than they emit, which is referred to as the EU's sink. Forests and agriculture land produce renewable biomass that can be used to substitute other carbon intensive products or to produce bioenergy, which in turn reduce greenhouse gas emissions from fossil fuels and industrial processes. Depending on how this biomass is produced, this can impact the size of the EU's sink, as well impact other services delivered by agriculture and forest land including biodiversity and ecosystem services.

In the context of a long term strategy please rank each land-use activities in the table below from 1 (important) to 5 (not important) to indicate which are acceptable and can be important to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase CO₂ absorptions (not all options need to be ranked):

	1	2	3	4	5
Forest as a source for biomass for renewable energy	<input type="radio"/>				
Forest as a source of material for bio-based products	<input type="radio"/>				
Forest as a carbon sink storing CO ₂	<input type="radio"/>				
Agriculture as a source of feedstock for bio-based materials	<input type="radio"/>				
Agriculture as a source for bio-energy	<input type="radio"/>				
based on food crops	<input type="radio"/>				
based on agricultural wastes	<input type="radio"/>				

based on woody biomass (e.g. perennials, woody and herbaceous crops, short rotation coppice)	<input type="radio"/>				
Protecting and enhancing soil carbon stocks on agricultural land	<input type="radio"/>				

What should be the role of the land-use sector in reducing emissions and increasing absorptions emissions? For what purposes should biomass be used most to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? How and which sustainability concerns should be addressed?

1000 character(s) maximum

Education, research and innovation

Considering the long time frame of the strategy, and the inherent magnitude of the decarbonisation transition, the central role of accelerating research and innovation for facilitating this transition will be crucial.

How best could awareness be raised to create the right attitude and values/ mind-sets?

at most 3 choice(s)

- At school through education
- Local and regional campaigning
- National and EU wide campaigning

On which sectors should R&D efforts focus primarily in the coming decade to best support the low carbon transition?

at most 6 choice(s)

- Energy
- Industrial processes
- Transport
- IT
- Agriculture
- Other field

On which cross-sectoral domains should R&D efforts focus in the coming decades? Is there a particular need for large scale deployment of certain innovative technologies? Is there a different role for authorities and private sector in support R&D and Innovation?

1000 character(s) maximum

There's urgent need for large scale deployment of reuse&recycling solutions with ecodesign and haz. subst removal, provided that EoL separation of materials is facilitated. Especially Biodegradable&Compostable applic. are relevant for traditional plastic applic. showing techn. and econ. constrains for recycling. R&D should focus on techn. develop. of renewable B&C materials production:

1. sustainable agricultural practices
2. increase biomass prod. eff. so as to not negatively influence biom. supply-demand of food/feed sectors
3. develop highly integrated and energy eff. processes along with use of RES for upstream.

Authorities should develop requirements for EPR schemes for B&C plastic products in the organic recycling route, and implement large scale pilots on public procurement.

Diffusion of private-public partnerships aimed at techn. exch. between MS can foster the developm. of closed-loop recycl. flows and multi-sectorial cascade recycling processes.

Financing

In many cases, the low carbon economy and energy transition needs high upfront investments with subsequent reductions in operating and fuel costs. In addition, this transition as well as climate change itself will most likely affect the value of existing investments and assets of companies. Finally, to achieve the transition efficiently, the viability and profitability of investments need to be ensured on the long-term. Most of these investments will have to be funded via private finance.

Will the sector that you are active in require significant additional investment in the context of a transition to a low carbon economy?

- Yes
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

For the sector that you are active in, is there a financing gap for making the transition to a low carbon economy?

- Yes
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

Should public sector be more involved in ensuring adequate financing for the low carbon transition?

- Yes, through direct investment
- Yes, through measures ensuring more low cost finance for sustainable investments
- No because of the risk of prompting inefficient investment leading to stranded assets
- No because of crowding effects on other sectors
- No opinion / I do not know

Would you consider that, in your sector, companies are sufficiently transparent about the financial risks they face due to climate change and the low carbon economy and energy transition?

- Yes
- No
- No opinion / I do not know

Meta trends

Do you think the following trends are important to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

Economic transition towards a more circular economy?

- Positive
- Negative
- Neutral

Digitalisation, including robotisation and artificial intelligence?

- Positive
- Negative
- Neutral

Shared economy?

- Positive
- Negative
- Neutral

Further interdependency of sectors across borders through globalisation?

- Positive
- Negative
- Neutral

Actors

Local authorities such as cities and local communities, as well as other actors such as civil society and the private sector, can play an important role in achieving the energy transformation, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change. Indeed thousands of cities, companies and citizens' organisations are implementing the low carbon economy and energy transition through projects covering energy, transport, food and waste management, often achieving important local co-benefits related to economic development, health and wellbeing.

Which of these non-state actors do you think will impact most your or your sector's contribution to delivering the EU's ambition to become a low carbon economy?

- Regional government
- Towns and cities
- Businesses
- Philanthropies
- Civil society (NGOs, ..)
- Religious groups

Do you have an example that you think is of particular importance to underline the role of such local and private sector actors in supporting the low carbon economy and energy transition?

1000 character(s) maximum

The partners of CIRC-PACK represent an example of the engagement and the fruitful collaboration of various local and private actors with different roles in the value chains of closed loops for plastic packaging, i. e. including plastic suppliers, converters, retailers, waste recovery managers from the public and the private sector, research and consumers organisations and non-profits. This diverse group of partners has joined forces to reinvent and develop more sustainable, re-usable forms of plastic packaging and support market uptake of the developed solutions. The aim is to promote a transition to a circular economy contributing to the achievement of EU waste management and recycling targets by 2030, in line with the strategic pillars of low carbon economy and energy transition.

Adaptation

The adverse effects of climate change will increase in the coming decades unless strong mitigation policies are implemented globally. In your place of living, which of the following actions do you think will be necessary to prepare for the likely effects of climate change? Please rank each option in the table below from 1 (important) to 5 (not important) to indicate which, in your place of living, you think will be necessary to prepare for the likely effects of climate change (not all options need to be ranked).

	1	2	3	4	5
Scientific research on the local effects of climate change in the place where you live	<input type="radio"/>				
Reinforcement of infrastructure (transport, energy, communication networks) to withstand natural disasters	<input type="radio"/>				
Preparation for floods (water retention, dykes, designated flood plains /areas, restriction of activities in areas at flood risks, floating houses etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Adaptation of agriculture to the changing climate (e.g. water efficient irrigation, selecting different crops)	<input type="radio"/>				
Heat wave action plans	<input type="radio"/>				
Increase of green areas in towns to cope with heatwaves / floods	<input type="radio"/>				
Encouragement of water saving and reuse	<input type="radio"/>				
Forest fire prevention (e.g. awareness raising campaigns, forest management...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Reinforcement and protection of the seacoast	<input type="radio"/>				
Early warning systems for natural disasters (heatwaves, floods, forest fires...)	<input type="radio"/>				
Communication to the public about the need to adapt to climate change	<input type="radio"/>				

Improved insurance products against damage from the effects of climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Better understanding of the security effects of climate change on the EU (e.g. flows of migrants, global water and food scarcity, agricultural trade)	<input type="radio"/>				

Which adaptation measures are of particular importance for your sector and why?

1000 character(s) maximum

Specific sectoral questions

These questions are focused on sector specific greenhouse gas reduction options, and as such are primarily directed to sectoral stakeholders.

Reducing industrial greenhouse emissions

Industry has a diverse set of greenhouse gas emissions sources, the majority are linked to energy consumption but also a significant amount of emissions comes from chemical processes, for instance in the steel, cement and chemical sectors.

Industry has a number of mitigation options to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions. These typically involve improved efficiency (e.g. using more efficient products and technologies, reusing waste heat, etc.) and fuel substitution (e.g. electrification of its processes). But it also includes feedstock substitution, be it with bio-material or by employing Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) technologies that see CO₂ emissions being re-used in other production processes. These technologies also often benefit from further integration of energy and industrial sectors.

Please indicate for which sector you see any of the above or other mitigation options of particular importance. Please indicate what your view is in terms of mitigation potential, economic potential and technology readiness. Assess each option as High, Medium, Low or Zero for each criterion and indicate in which year you think the technology would be ready for large scale deployment.

	Industrial Sector	Technology option	Mitigation potential	Economic viability	Technology readiness	Year of large scale deployment
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						

Reducing greenhouse emissions from transport

Transport has a number of options to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions. While low- or zero-emission technologies are already successfully deployed for parts of the transport sector (e.g. cars and vans), the technological development is in earlier stages of development or deployment for other parts of the transport sector (e.g. long-haul trucks, aviation or maritime).

Please indicate for which part of the transport sector you see particular mitigation options and their importance. Please indicate what your view is in terms of mitigation potential, economic potential and technology readiness. Assess each option as High, Medium, Low or Zero for each criterion and indicate in which year you think the technology would be ready for large scale deployment.

	Transport Sector	Technology option	Mitigation potential	Economic viability	Technology readiness	Year of large scale deployment
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						

In addition, would you please indicate your choice for the following options that allow reducing the energy consumption and related CO₂ emissions?

For freight transport, would you consider switching from road to alternative modes like rail, waterways or coastal shipping?

- Yes
- No, too slow or complicated
- No, too expensive
- No opinion / I do not know

For first/last mile logistics in urban areas, would you consider switching from road to alternative modes like (electric) cargo bike or similar zero-emission vehicle?

- Yes, I am already doing it
- Yes, in the future
- No, too slow
- No
- No opinion / I don't know

Reducing greenhouse emissions from agriculture

Several options exist to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in agriculture even though the mitigation potential of the agricultural sector, notably related to the sector's non-CO₂ emissions, is seen as more limited than for other sectors. Furthermore, agriculture is a sector that through its impact on land use also will affect how our natural sink, and thus the related CO₂ absorptions, will evolve.

Please indicate which mitigation options are of particular importance. Assess each option as High, Medium, Low or Zero for each criterion and indicate in which year you think the technology would be ready for large scale deployment.

	Agriculture sector	Technology option	Mitigation potential	Economic viability	Technology readiness	Year of large scale deployment
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						

Role of CO₂ removal

The objectives of the Paris Agreement are challenging and many scientists consider that it will be necessary at a certain point to remove a significant amount of CO₂ from the atmosphere in order to stay below 2°C and certainly in case the temperature increase should be limited to 1.5°C. There are a limited number of options to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere.

The removal of CO₂ can be accomplished by 1) capturing CO₂ via natural photosynthesis or artificial chemical processes, and then 2) storing CO₂ in long term geological sites or within biomass and (bio) materials.

Rank from 1 (important) to 5 (not important) on what role you think this removal and storage options can have in the EU to deliver negative emissions taking into account issues such as economic and technical feasibility, storage potential, environmental integrity and social acceptance.

Capture of CO₂ from the atmosphere

	1	2	3	4	5
Intensive afforestation	<input type="radio"/>				
Forest and cropland residues	<input type="radio"/>				
Woody perennial plantations	<input type="radio"/>				
Direct Air Capture	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

Storage of CO₂

	1	2	3	4	5
Carbon capture and storage (CCS) with enhanced oil or gas recovery	<input type="radio"/>				
CCS in onshore geological sites	<input type="radio"/>				
CCS in offshore geological sites	<input type="radio"/>				
Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) (long lived products)	<input type="radio"/>				
Increased permanent carbon stock in soils	<input type="radio"/>				
Increased permanent carbon stock in plants	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

What main barriers do you see currently preventing the large scale deployment of CCS, including on how to use it to generate negative emissions? What are the particular challenges related to biomass CCS? What type of CCU (Carbon Capture and Utilization) would lend itself to create long term storage? Are there other technologies that should also be considered? What policies do you think the EU should pursue to better help development and deployment?

1000 character(s) maximum

Additional Comments

If you wish to add further information, comments or suggestions - within the scope of this questionnaire - please feel free to do so here:

1000 character(s) maximum

CIRC-PACK project included citizen consultations to evaluate chance of success of the proposed solutions on the market. 1st survey was carried out btw Nov17-Jan18 in 6 countries (Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Spain, Croatia and Kartal district-Turkey) to investigate current habits regarding product packaging and when purchasing or segregating domestic waste. Additionally, the survey intended to measure awareness and level of information regarding environmental policies or impact of plastics & plastic packaging. A special section was dedicated on current habits and problems with current plastic packaging. Consumers potential behaviour regarding new plastic materials, such as bio-based, recycled or biodegradable packaging materials has been analysed. Acceptance, pricing and information on project demo-case products has been investigated.

Conclusions from 9869 valid questionnaires, representative by gender, age, studies and geographical distribution in each region have been obtained.

In addition, you could also upload a document proving further information, comments or suggestions:

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Contact

CLIMA-ENER-LONG-TERM-STRATEGY@ec.europa.eu

	Document:	D6.6 Update of the legislative barriers for the recycling of fossil based and biobased plastics for packaging and policy recommendations		
	Author:	RINA-C	Version	0.0
	Reference:	D6.6	Date:	26/5/20

Attachment to the Consultation (as uploaded)

ANNEX - CONCLUSIONS (as published on Deliverable 2.3)

CIRC-PACK innovations can help to address consumers' sustainability needs. Most people agree that current production, use and waste of plastic for domestic use cause pollution problems. Plastic for domestic use is considered a problem for the planet in all countries and it is also considered to use a lot of natural resources. Additionally, environmental aspects exert a moderate influence on the decision of buying everyday products such as food, detergents or hygiene products. Besides, environment is a relevant aspect of packaging that citizens value in all countries, but Croatia and Kartal. Therefore, a more sustainable plastic packaging can be part of a more sustainable consumption.

Since new plastic materials a very limited market share and there is little available information about their properties, it is understandable that **most of respondents do not consider new plastic materials as a first option when buying most demo-case products**, except in Italia where biodegradable alternatives are the prevalent option. In other countries more than 50% of respondents would prefer conventional options or do not have a clear preference when being asked about the type of packaging they would choose. Information about properties and advantages becomes key for success of these initiatives towards a more sustainable consumption.

Citizens would clearly **prefer biodegradable options** over bio-based products. The best acceptance for a biodegradable packaging product relates to coffee capsules. There is a willingness to pay a little bit more for these new packaging options, although a significant share of respondents would pay no single amount. The average amount varies across countries but not significantly between products, except for coffee capsules for which people would pay slightly less extra.

The sorting of biodegradable **plastic with bio-waste is not perceived to have a negative impact on the domestic waste management** for most respondents. There is a good level of waste sorting (including plastic fraction) in Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain. In Croatia and Kartal sorting scores significantly lower. Main constraints are the inconvenience to have so many waste bins at home and the distance to the bring-points. However, a different sorting for biodegradable packaging does not seem a barrier.

Information has a key role to play but finding trust-inspiring information channels is equally important. Most citizens consider they are not at all or not well informed about new plastic materials, whereas a third of them would like to be informed. Respondents do not trust in information given by manufacturers, supermarkets or media and they have more confidence in environmental and consumer organizations. Public authorities score fairly, especially in Portugal and Kartal. Information needs to be reinforced in order to move citizens into action. Most respondents find it very important having a good ecological behaviour but many of them do not take a lot of actions to put this into practice